

AZORES DEESEA RESEARCH

**MAPGES 2024 CRUISE REPORT: EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA
BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES ON-BOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO**

INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO EM CIÊNCIAS DO MAR - OKEANOS, UNIVERSIDADE DOS AÇORES, HORTA, PORTUGAL

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1 SUMMARY OF THE MAPGES 2024 CRUISE ON BOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO

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1.1 MAIN OBJECTIVES

MapGES 2024 is the continuation of our long-term strategy to map deep-sea biodiversity and identify Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) in the Azores using the Azor drift-cam imagery system. In this cruise, we operated, once again, from the RV Arquipélago and planned to visit some unexplored areas along the Alberto do Mónaco ridge, Princesa Alice, and some other areas along the Mid Atlantic Ridge. We aimed to expand previous explorations of these areas into deeper waters. During Leg 1, we visited Princesa Alice SW, Monte Alto, Espadarte, Farpas, Monte Alto SE, Monte Baixo, Voador, and Alberto Mónaco N. In Leg 2, we visited Princesa Alice, Princesa Alice S and Princesa Alice SE. Leg 3, aimed to visit Mar da Prata bank, D. João de Castro, and Heitor Álvares seamounts but was cancelled because of problems in the hydraulic which of the vessel. In leg 4, we visited Boureé NE, Boureé E, Princesa Alice, Princesa Alice S, Princesa Alice W, De Guerne, Açor S, Açor, Óscar, Bicuda, and Ferradura. As in other MapGES cruises, the objectives were to (i) map benthic communities inhabiting unexplored seamounts, ridges, and island slopes, (ii) identify new areas that fit the FAO Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem definition; and (iii) determine distribution patterns of deep-sea benthic biodiversity in the Azores. The results of this cruise added to the previous contributions to identify the environmental drivers that determine the spatial distribution of deep-sea benthic biodiversity in the Azores. It also provides valuable information in the context of Good Environmental Status (GES), Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and new insights on how to sustainably manage deep-sea ecosystems.

1.2 METHODOLOGY

We performed several underwater video transects along the seafloor with the Azor drift-cam, a low-cost drifting camera system designed and developed at IMAR & IICM Okeanos at the University of the Azores. It allowed recording high-quality underwater video images of the seabed down to 1000 m depth. The system was deployed from the Research Vessel Arquipélago, owned by the Government of the Azores. In each of the areas or geomorphological structures to be explored, a representative number of dives (or transects) were carried out with a video camera system from a depth of about 1 000 m to the shallowest depth of each structure. The objective is to obtain underwater images to characterize the biodiversity along the entire bathymetric gradient and substrate types of each structure. The video transects were planned according to the best bathymetry available, so that the camera systems move from deeper to shallower areas. This methodology allows the collected images to always have the best possible quality, maximizing the area of incidence of light and avoiding its dissipation in the water column (in the case of descending transects). The transects carried out with the

Azor-drift-cam were planned to last approximately 60 min in the seafloor, with the system drifting over the benthic habitats at an approximate speed of 0.5 to 1 knot. Under normal oceanographic conditions, each working day allowed for 5 to 6 dives, corresponding to around 5 km of bottom explored per day.

Vessel

RV Arquipélago

Dates

Leg 1: 6th to 15th July

Leg 2: 17th to 31st July

Leg 3: Cancelled (Planned: 12th August to 24th August)

Leg 4: 24th August to 7th September

Scientific team:

Leg 1: Telmo Morato (chief scientist), Guilherme Gonçalves, Marc Pladevall Vilavendrell, Rachel Lacoste, Sérgio Gomes

Leg 2: Carlos Dominguez-Carrió (chief scientist), Luís Rodrigues, Manuela Ramos, Gabriela Cardoso, Marina Navarro Engesser

Leg 4: Guilherme Gonçalves (chief scientist), Luís Rodrigues (chief scientist), Sérgio Gomes, Manuela Ramos, Gabriela Cardoso, Gerald H. Taranto

1.3 STATISTICS

Altogether, we performed 144 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1150 m depth, covering 83 km of the seafloor and producing more than 129 hours of video footage of the seabed.

Leg 1: We performed 48 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1100 m depth, covering 28 km of the seafloor and producing 48 hours of video footage, 2.66TB of disc space.

Leg 2: We performed 33 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1016 m depth, covering 22 km of the seafloor and producing 28:44 hours of video footage, 1.84TB of disc space.

Leg 3: Cancelled

Leg 4: We performed 64 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1150 m depth, covering 33 km of the seafloor and producing 62 hours of video footage, 3.2 TB of disc space.

Figure 1. Scientific teams that participated in the different legs of the MapGES 2024 Cruises on the RV Arquipélago.

1.4 CRUISE SUMMARY

The MapGES 2024 cruise onboard RV Arquipélago was composed of 4 Legs, which were planned to visit some unexplored areas along the Alberto do Mónaco Ridge, the Princesa Alice bank and its surrounding areas and some seamounts along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (Table 1). Overall, 144 dives out of 145 stations were accomplished in 20 sampling areas (Table 2). During **Leg 1**, from 6th to 15th July 2024, we performed 47 successful dives with the Azor drift-cam. During this Leg, we managed to perform the 1000th dive with the Azor drift-cam, as well as the farthest ever from land. Unfortunately, we lost one complete Azor drift-cam system (the fourth since we started operating the system back in 2019) due to entanglement on lost longlines near a vertical wall. During Leg 1 we surveyed the deep-sea benthic communities dwelling on the geomorphological structures along the Alberto do Mónaco Ridge on board of the research vessel Arquipélago. During **Leg 2**, from 17th to 31st July 2024, we performed 31 successful dives with the Azor drift-cam. **Leg 2** of the MapGES 2024 cruise explored the Princesa Alice bank areas, but the weather conditions severely limited our operations in this important Azorean fishing ground. **Leg 3** of the MapGES 2024 was canceled due to multiple technical issues related to the research vessel Arquipélago, which prevented us from carrying out our work. **Leg 4** of the MapGES 2024 cruise was composed of two parts. During the first half of **Leg 4**, from 24th to 30th August 2024, we performed 43 successful dives with the Azor drift-cam, continuing the exploration of the Princesa Alice bank and expanding our work to its surrounding areas. During the second half of **Leg 4**, from 3rd to 6th September 2024, we performed 21 successful dives in some seamounts along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, including Óscar, Bicuda and Ferradura. During The MapGES 2024 cruise we observed very diverse benthic and fish communities

including dense coral gardens of the primnoids *Narella bellissima* and *Narella versluysi*, large black-corals of the species *Leiopathes glaberrima*, aggregations of black-corals *Leiopathes expansa*, bubblegum corals *Paragorgia johnsoni*, and *Placogorgia* sp. On the top of several mounts we drifted over coral reefs of the scleractinian *Eguchipsammia formosa* and vast fields of the bird’s nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri*. Occasionally, we sighted the rarely seen sailfin roughsharks of the species *Oxynotus paradoxus*, the swordfish *Xiphias gladius* and the first ever recorded footage with the Azor drift-cam of a Risso’s smooth-head cf. *Alepocephalus rostratus*.

Table 1. Areas surveyed during each of the Legs of MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago, with information on the number of dives, total distance of seafloor covered, and number of hours recording video footage on the seafloor.

Leg	Dates	Areas explored	Dives (n)	Dist. (km)	Bottom time (hh:mm)
1	06/07/2024 15/07/2024	– Geomorphological structures along the Alberto do Mónaco Ridge: Princesa Alice SW, Monte Alto, Monte Alto SE, Espadarte, Farpas, Monte Baixo, Voador, Alberto do Mónaco N	48	28	48:00
2	17/07/2024 31/07/2024	– Marine Robotics Workshop and Geomorphological structures of Princesa Alice Bank: Princesa Alice, SE, S	33	22	29:00
3	12/08/2024 24/08/2024	– Cancelled	-	-	-
4	24/08/2024 07/09/2024	– Geomorphological structures of the Princesa Alice Bank, Mid-Atlantic Ridge: Princesa Alice, S, W, De Guerne, Açor, S, Óscar, Bicuda, Ferradura	64	33	62:00
Total			145	83	139:00

Figure 2. Location of the 144 video transects carried out with the Azor drift-cam during the MapGES 2024 cruises on-board the RV Arquipélago.

Figure 3. Screenshots taken from the footage recorded during the MapGES 2024 cruise onboard the RV Arquipélago. (a) Large colony of the black coral *Leiopathes glaberrima* used as a refuge by a small fish; (b) Slope densely colonized by a vast coral garden of *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*; (c) Diverse coral community dominated by *Candidella imbricata*, with *Madrepora oculata* and *Lophelia pertusa* colonies also present; (d) Aggregations of black-corals *Leiopathes expansa*, and *Placogorgia* sp. colonizing deep and steep slopes (e) Large aggregation of *Acanthogorgia* spp. together with a high diversity of soft corals; (f) A vast and dense field of the hexactinellid *Pheronema carpenteri* (g) Massive demosponges *Characella pachastrelloides* displaying their usual funnel morphology; (h) First ever recorded image of the a Risso's smooth-head cf. *Alepocephalus rostratus* with the Azor drift-cam; (i) Elusive swordfish *Xiphias gladius*.

1.5 MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS

1. During the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago, we were able to perform 144 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1100 m depth, where we explored about 83 km of the seafloor and produced 139 hours of video footage. This year, we performed the **farthest dive ever from land on the southwest tip of the Alberto do Mónaco ridge**, in Espadarte area.
2. On July 12th 2024, we achieved an impressive and unbelievable milestone: **the dive 1000 with the Azor drift-cam**. Back in 2018 when we started to design a low-cost system to provide us with some images of the seafloor of the Azores, we never expected that only 6 years later we would have visited all geomorphological structures shallower than 1000 m and produced one of the world's most comprehensive dataset of deep-sea benthic megafauna biodiversity distribution.
3. In Espadarte seamount we **lost one complete Azor drift-cam system**; the fourth since we started operating the system back in 2019. In station 16, we got entangled on several lost fishing lines and a steep wall. We could see several lost multifilament lines hanging from the wall and spent about 2 hours trying to get it free but with no success, since the umbilical broke on the hydraulic winch. This is yet another example of the volume of lost fishing lines in really steep slopes of the Azores seamounts and the impact they have in deep-sea exploration. After this unfortunate event, we cancelled the dives for the rest of the day, prepared a new set of the Azor drift-cam, and were ready to go.

4. Although, the video annotations still have to be finished, it seems that we **confirmed Farpas seamount as one of the areas in the Azores with higher densities of the primnoid corals *Narella bellissima* and *Narella versluysi***. In 2022, we were stunned by the impressive high abundances of the primnoid corals *Narella* spp. observed in this seamount with the NIOZ towed camera system, during the iMAR Eurofleets+ cruise. It was with no surprise but with great joy that the Azor drift-cam dives confirmed that similar ridges in the Farpas seamount host similar high abundances of these species. Remarkably, the density of these corals frequently exceeded 10 colonies per square meter, accompanied by a diverse array of other benthic species. This observation reinforces **the ecological significance of this area and highlights the rich biodiversity** found within the deep-sea environments of the Azores.
5. We were caught by surprise with **occasional rocky outcrops filmed at the deep and flat Alberto do Mónaco N area teeming with benthic fauna with patches of impressive biodiversity**. The expectations for the biodiversity explorations in this area were low, given the flat and deep nature of the structures. However, on a couple of rocks we observed black corals *Leiopathes expansa* with *Madrepora oculata*, *Paramuricea*, and *Candidella imbricata*.
6. The “bird’s nest” glass sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* was, likely, the most conspicuous species observed **during this Cruise**. This sponge was frequently seen occupying the deeper strata samples, between 650 and 1000m depth, in small to large patches over soft bottoms. Not surprisingly, this species is one of the most common records in our deep-sea biodiversity occurrence database.
7. **We finally explore more thoroughly a large area that includes Princesa Alice and Açor banks**, achieving a total of 74 successful dives in these and their vast surrounding areas. Despite being the most heavily fished grounds of the Azores archipelago, these areas **showed a high diversity of megabenthic fauna and communities**, across all depth strata explored.
8. We also reached the goal of exploring the deeper sectors of some seamounts of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. Back in 2019, the exploration of the seamounts that compose this large mountain chain was confined to 600m depth, which meant that the exploration of these areas still lacked in representativeness. During this cruise, we wanted to complement these past surveys with the exploration of deeper strata, thus making the survey of these areas more complete. Indeed, these sectors revealed **diverse benthic communities of several coral species** such as large *Paragorgia johnsoni*, *Leiopathes expansa*, *Placogorgia* sp., *Lophelia pertusa*, *Madrepora oculata*, *Hemicorallium niobe*, *H. tricolor*, *Pleurocorallium johnsoni*, and *Pseudoanthomathus* sp., revealing the presence of **unique fragile and vulnerable deep-sea ecosystems along the MAR**. Óscar, Bicuda and Ferradura seamounts contained other relevant benthic assemblages, including dense ***Narella* spp. gardens** and **great abundances of *Acanthogorgia* spp.**, for instance.
9. Unfortunately, the goal of visiting the **Mar da Prata bank and the D. João de Castro and Heitor Álvares seamounts** during Leg 3 could not be achieved due to **technical reasons related with the RV Arquipélago hydraulic system**, which stopped working during Leg 2 of this cruise. As the issue remained unsolved for more than 20 days, this resulted in a significant setback on our planned work for most of this cruise, with **Leg 3 ending up cancelled entirely and Leg 4 having to be adapted to compensate for a shorter Leg 2**.

1.6 STATIONS SURVEYED DURING THE MAPGES 2024 CRUISE ONBOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO

In the MapGES 2024 survey we conducted, 144 dives out of 145 stations in 21 sampling areas. Here we present a compilation of all the stations surveyed during this cruise (Table 2).

Table 2. Compilation of the stations surveyed during MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago.

Station	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End position		Depth (m)		Dist. (m)
			Start	End	Lat. (N)	Long. (W)	Lat. (N)	Long. (W)	start	End	
St001	Princesa Alice SW	06/07/2024	09:04	11:16	37.864	-29.818	37.864	-29.819	950	908	150
St002	Princesa Alice SW	06/07/2024	11:39	13:39	37.855	-29.808	37.851	-29.803	1008	1061	570
St003	Princesa Alice SW	06/07/2024	14:10	15:49	37.850	-29.858	37.848	-29.852	775	780	590
St004	Princesa Alice SW	06/07/2024	16:13	17:53	37.824	-29.896	37.818	-29.890	935	845	850
St005	Princesa Alice SW	06/07/2024	18:09	19:34	37.823	-29.899	37.822	-29.898	958	904	110
St006	Monte Alto	07/07/2024	07:57	09:41	37.264	-31.406	37.257	-31.405	690	608	800
St007	Monte Alto	07/07/2024	10:24	12:26	37.319	-31.436	37.314	-31.432	1100	842	650
St008	Monte Alto	07/07/2024	13:04	14:50	37.336	-31.499	37.335	-31.493	950	864	550
St009	Monte Alto	07/07/2024	15:05	16:36	37.320	-31.504	37.314	-31.499	664	580	800
St010	Monte Alto	07/07/2024	16:55	18:16	37.271	-31.490	37.266	-31.491	877	840	600
St011	Monte Alto	07/07/2024	18:34	19:27	37.268	-31.482	37.265	-31.482	650	660	330
St012	Espadarte	08/07/2024	08:01	09:45	36.752	-32.657	36.747	-32.653	941	730	600
St013	Espadarte	08/07/2024	10:16	11:35	36.777	-32.628	36.774	-32.628	820	724	330
St014	Espadarte	08/07/2024	11:49	13:20	36.779	-32.602	36.771	-32.598	795	809	880
St015	Espadarte	08/07/2024	13:52	15:26	36.806	-32.567	36.800	-32.561	632	541	870
St016*	Espadarte	08/07/2024	15:47	NA	36.823	-32.539	36.822	-32.538	770	NA	220
St017	Farpas	09/07/2024	08:07	09:52	36.899	-32.239	36.896	-32.235	935	940	460
St018	Farpas	09/07/2024	10:17	12:20	36.928	-32.209	36.927	-32.201	844	640	720
St019	Farpas	09/07/2024	13:14	15:05	36.954	-32.097	36.953	-32.088	918	700	750
St020	Farpas	09/07/2024	15:26	16:48	36.964	-32.067	36.960	-32.062	655	607	630
St021	Farpas	09/07/2024	17:23	18:47	36.995	-32.002	36.992	-31.995	900	662	700
St022	Monte Alto SE	10/07/2024	07:54	09:25	37.041	-31.767	37.036	-31.770	990	827	610
St023	Monte Alto SE	10/07/2024	09:51	11:38	37.051	-31.742	37.047	-31.743	880	662	480
St024	Monte Alto SE	10/07/2024	12:21	13:41	37.084	-31.661	37.081	-31.661	866	940	380
St025	Monte Alto SE	10/07/2024	14:03	15:51	37.099	-31.632	37.095	-31.633	774	863	450
St026	Monte Alto	10/07/2024	16:37	18:32	37.147	-31.563	37.141	-31.569	873	747	800
St027	Monte Baixo	11/07/2024	07:57	09:16	37.384	-31.271	37.384	-31.275	784	722	330
St028	Monte Baixo	11/07/2024	09:42	10:59	37.387	-31.231	37.390	-31.237	616	626	610
St029	Monte Baixo	11/07/2024	11:16	13:09	37.375	-31.238	37.377	-31.247	850	689	840
St030	Monte Baixo	11/07/2024	13:30	14:59	37.390	-31.208	37.396	-31.213	695	630	780
St031	Monte Baixo	11/07/2024	15:12	16:34	37.387	-31.218	37.391	-31.219	623	590	490
St032	Monte Baixo	11/07/2024	16:59	18:01	37.378	-31.172	37.379	-31.170	960	948	200
St033	Monte Baixo	11/07/2024	18:08	19:22	37.385	-31.168	37.385	-31.161	936	862	660
St034	Monte Baixo	12/07/2024	07:55	09:13	37.404	-31.158	37.400	-31.153	733	717	620
St035	Monte Baixo	12/07/2024	09:42	11:25	37.427	-31.140	37.425	-31.135	763	580	550
St036	Monte Baixo	12/07/2024	11:41	13:27	37.436	-31.120	37.437	-31.116	910	871	410
St037	Monte Baixo	12/07/2024	13:36	15:25	37.435	-31.104	37.436	-31.097	761	676	600
St038	Monte Baixo	12/07/2024	16:05	18:19	37.387	-31.011	37.388	-31.003	1010	843	780
St039	Voador	13/07/2024	07:54	09:22	37.451	-30.906	37.444	-30.902	525	478	830
St040	Voador	13/07/2024	10:20	12:35	37.538	-30.839	37.533	-30.841	1050	928	630
St041	Voador	13/07/2024	13:22	14:59	37.543	-30.739	37.538	-30.737	298	262	600
St042	Voador	13/07/2024	15:36	16:32	37.594	-30.684	37.593	-30.684	925	924	70
St043	Voador	13/07/2024	16:52	19:03	37.591	-30.684	37.581	-30.678	906	711	1270
St044	Alberto do Mónaco N	14/07/2024	07:49	09:36	37.583	-30.329	37.582	-30.330	953	956	170
St045	Alberto do Mónaco N	14/07/2024	09:52	11:34	37.585	-30.325	37.590	-30.324	954	974	550
St046	Alberto do Mónaco N	14/07/2024	11:56	14:04	37.630	-30.312	37.636	-30.308	942	955	840
St047	Alberto do Mónaco N	14/07/2024	15:00	17:14	37.701	-30.163	37.708	-30.157	930	890	940
St048	Alberto do Mónaco N	14/07/2024	17:35	19:56	37.750	-30.139	37.751	-30.134	903	983	500
St049	Faial-Pico S (Robotics)	17/07/2024	10:44	11:21	38.472	-28.592	38.469	-28.592	380	350	310
St050	Faial-Pico S (Robotics)	17/07/2024	15:18	15:55	38.471	-28.587	38.469	-28.588	380	350	260
St051	Princesa Alice SE	19/07/2024	08:25	09:25	37.704	-28.978	37.706	-28.978	343	340	220
St052	Princesa Alice SE	19/07/2024	10:54	11:50	37.653	-29.025	37.651	-29.024	816	822	310
St053	Princesa Alice SE	19/07/2024	12:51	13:40	37.634	-29.001	37.629	-28.996	642	684	660

Station	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End position		Depth (m)		Dist. (m)
			Start	End	Lat. (N)	Long. (W)	Lat. (N)	Long. (W)	start	End	
St054	Princesa Alice SE	19/07/2024	14:42	15:41	37.640	-28.921	37.634	-28.925	398	372	800
St055	Princesa Alice SE	19/07/2024	16:55	17:47	37.622	-28.808	37.616	-28.808	840	736	670
St056	Princesa Alice SE	19/07/2024	18:28	19:10	37.638	-28.827	37.633	-28.827	682	675	470
St057	Princesa Alice SE	20/07/2024	08:45	10:24	37.766	-28.896	37.757	-28.889	866	726	1110
St058	Princesa Alice SE	20/07/2024	11:22	11:50	37.768	-28.949	37.765	-28.948	543	439	360
St059	Princesa Alice SE	20/07/2024	12:44	13:48	37.769	-29.024	37.761	-29.014	400	321	1200
St060	Princesa Alice	20/07/2024	14:45	15:38	37.806	-29.065	37.800	-29.056	525	588	1010
St061	Princesa Alice SE	20/07/2024	16:55	17:20	37.772	-29.129	37.769	-29.127	569	448	340
St062	Princesa Alice SE	20/07/2024	18:20	19:14	37.752	-29.158	37.749	-29.162	501	458	500
St063	Princesa Alice	21/07/2024	08:19	09:34	37.835	-29.103	37.831	-29.106	446	344	540
St064	Princesa Alice	21/07/2024	10:46	11:28	37.879	-29.090	37.883	-29.086	668	734	540
St065	Princesa Alice	21/07/2024	12:16	13:17	37.882	-29.116	37.885	-29.113	556	480	400
St066	Princesa Alice	21/07/2024	14:10	15:20	37.911	-29.044	37.912	-29.036	899	809	700
St067	Princesa Alice	21/07/2024	16:33	17:38	37.932	-29.066	37.925	-29.063	991	777	780
St068	Princesa Alice	21/07/2024	18:38	19:15	37.941	-29.119	37.936	-29.116	568	326	590
St069	Princesa Alice	22/07/2024	08:35	09:54	38.032	-29.189	38.025	-29.195	914	679	870
St070	Princesa Alice	22/07/2024	10:43	12:16	38.018	-29.238	38.013	-29.239	500	392	480
St071	Princesa Alice	22/07/2024	13:00	14:30	37.970	-29.261	37.970	-29.248	368	280	1120
St072	Princesa Alice	22/07/2024	15:06	15:45	37.963	-29.284	37.963	-29.279	448	399	460
St073	Princesa Alice	22/07/2024	16:48	17:25	37.993	-29.352	37.990	-29.348	589	625	550
St074	Princesa Alice	22/07/2024	18:24	19:26	38.010	-29.302	38.004	-29.301	127	78	680
St075	Princesa Alice S	23/07/2024	08:22	09:35	37.901	-29.451	37.904	-29.463	565	622	1090
St076	Princesa Alice S	23/07/2024	10:26	11:04	37.875	-29.476	37.879	-29.481	453	502	660
St077	Princesa Alice S	23/07/2024	12:59	13:34	37.823	-29.485	37.826	-29.483	613	639	440
St078	Princesa Alice S	23/07/2024	14:58	15:40	37.778	-29.525	37.782	-29.518	1016	863	680
St079	Agulhas 12 Milhas	31/07/2024	09:59	10:54	38.309	-28.740	38.302	-28.736	464	496	850
St080	Agulhas 12 Milhas	31/07/2024	11:52	12:49	38.284	-28.684	38.281	-28.692	824	884	830
St081	Açor	31/07/2024	14:48	15:20	38.223	-28.875	38.220	-28.874	952	849	380
St082	Bouree NE	24/08/2024	08:35	09:35	38.375	-29.337	38.368	-29.339	900	750	770
St083	Bouree NE	24/08/2024	10:29	11:47	38.342	-29.360	38.337	-29.364	924	890	620
St084	Bouree E	24/08/2024	12:47	14:21	38.331	-29.408	38.333	-29.409	905	882	240
St085	Bouree E	24/08/2024	15:46	16:18	38.268	-29.460	38.264	-29.461	667	699	430
St086	Bouree E	24/08/2024	17:10	18:41	38.254	-29.482	38.249	-29.487	696	623	640
St087	Bouree E	25/08/2024	08:32	09:32	38.212	-29.278	38.215	-29.279	651	595	340
St088	Bouree E	25/08/2024	10:50	11:20	38.218	-29.401	38.219	-29.399	651	595	140
St089	Bouree E	25/08/2024	12:46	13:57	38.135	-29.405	38.133	-29.404	1055	975	350
St090	Bouree E	25/08/2024	15:02	16:13	38.141	-29.385	38.143	-29.383	440	370	330
St091	Bouree E	25/08/2024	16:51	17:26	38.118	-29.364	38.116	-29.364	697	795	220
St092	Bouree E	25/08/2024	18:22	18:59	38.095	-29.332	38.096	-29.333	654	612	120
St093	Princesa Alice	26/08/2024	07:58	09:40	37.908	-29.188	37.907	-29.181	280	241	620
St094	Princesa Alice	26/08/2024	10:24	11:52	37.896	-29.147	37.895	-29.145	280	241	270
St095	Princesa Alice	26/08/2024	13:08	13:24	37.897	-29.247	37.898	-29.247	331	330	30
St096	Princesa Alice	26/08/2024	14:01	14:48	37.889	-29.252	37.888	-29.252	364	355	120
St097	Princesa Alice	26/08/2024	15:41	16:38	37.939	-29.302	37.941	-29.297	356	355	530
St098	Princesa Alice	26/08/2024	17:05	17:40	37.930	-29.306	37.932	-29.299	270	355	670
St099	Princesa Alice	26/08/2024	18:19	19:02	37.909	-29.329	37.910	-29.321	376	277	710
St100	Princesa Alice S	27/08/2024	08:02	08:58	37.842	-29.359	37.840	-29.355	445	382	470
St101	Princesa Alice S	27/08/2024	09:52	10:49	37.850	-29.384	37.846	-29.382	613	559	470
St102	Princesa Alice S	27/08/2024	11:42	12:38	37.839	-29.434	37.836	-29.438	512	410	530
St103	Princesa Alice W	27/08/2024	13:56	14:55	37.916	-29.513	37.913	-29.515	640	605	450
St104	Princesa Alice W	27/08/2024	15:56	16:49	37.964	-29.498	37.963	-29.501	514	498	310
St105	Princesa Alice W	27/08/2024	17:58	19:13	38.026	-29.567	38.029	-29.573	1040	940	640
St106	De Guerne	28/08/2024	08:15	09:04	37.884	-28.694	37.885	-28.691	380	362	260
St107	De Guerne	28/08/2024	09:47	11:00	37.875	-28.742	37.876	-28.735	637	502	610
St108	De Guerne	28/08/2024	11:44	12:03	37.905	-28.776	37.904	-28.776	497	394	140
St109	De Guerne	28/08/2024	12:52	14:02	37.930	-28.828	37.926	-28.823	497	394	660
St110	De Guerne	28/08/2024	14:47	15:36	37.950	-28.811	37.947	-28.809	709	577	360
St111	De Guerne	28/08/2024	16:29	17:41	37.921	-28.865	37.917	-28.863	923	756	440
St112	De Guerne	28/08/2024	18:20	18:42	37.913	-28.890	37.914	-28.889	677	721	150
St113	Açor S	29/08/2024	08:22	09:22	38.213	-29.154	38.216	-29.157	800	733	460

Station	Location	Date	Time		Start position		End position		Depth (m)		Dist. (m)
			Start	End	Lat. (N)	Long. (W)	Lat. (N)	Long. (W)	start	End	
St114	Açor S	29/08/2024	10:22	11:17	38.182	-29.217	38.186	-29.218	740	720	410
St115	Açor S	29/08/2024	12:14	13:16	38.134	-29.241	38.138	-29.236	617	583	610
St116	Açor S	29/08/2024	14:16	15:06	38.152	-29.161	38.155	-29.157	428	387	530
St117	Açor S	29/08/2024	15:51	16:22	38.154	-29.090	38.157	-29.089	458	387	320
St118	Açor S	29/08/2024	16:50	17:55	38.147	-29.064	38.151	-29.063	468	397	410
St119	Açor S	30/08/2024	08:21	09:21	38.073	-28.999	38.078	-28.997	500	289	640
St120	Açor	30/08/2024	09:57	11:00	38.123	-28.995	38.127	-28.991	458	362	570
St121	Açor	30/08/2024	11:42	12:34	38.136	-28.925	38.139	-28.922	702	570	390
St122	Açor	30/08/2024	13:24	14:21	38.147	-28.873	38.152	-28.868	852	782	610
St123	Açor	30/08/2024	15:13	16:01	38.158	-28.919	38.160	-28.916	489	378	310
St124	Açor	30/08/2024	16:36	17:25	38.173	-28.923	38.174	-28.921	298	286	180
St125	Óscar	03/09/2024	09:02	10:31	39.603	-29.300	39.599	-29.306	859	742	670
St126	Óscar	03/09/2024	11:12	11:24	39.612	-29.318	39.611	-29.319	874	865	130
St127	Óscar	03/09/2024	12:08	13:23	39.612	-29.317	39.605	-29.322	885	711	810
St128	Óscar	03/09/2024	14:11	15:11	39.607	-29.338	39.599	-29.347	643	577	1170
St129	Óscar	03/09/2024	16:09	17:30	39.627	-29.342	39.619	-29.349	1055	721	1000
St130	Óscar	03/09/2024	18:07	19:10	39.611	-29.356	39.605	-29.364	685	531	960
St131	Óscar	04/09/2024	08:09	08:56	39.627	-29.435	39.625	-29.442	667	789	670
St132	Óscar	04/09/2024	09:55	11:21	39.640	-29.425	39.637	-29.434	912	672	890
St133	Óscar	04/09/2024	12:09	13:09	39.631	-29.417	39.625	-29.421	935	829	700
St134	Óscar	04/09/2024	14:06	15:38	39.628	-29.397	39.620	-29.402	1010	708	1000
St135	Óscar	04/09/2024	16:33	17:40	39.621	-29.364	39.616	-29.370	813	645	760
St136	Óscar	04/09/2024	18:17	19:10	39.617	-29.378	39.611	-29.383	830	774	710
St137	Bicuda	05/09/2024	08:14	09:32	38.495	-30.389	38.496	-30.398	997	929	750
St138	Bicuda	05/09/2024	10:26	11:40	38.478	-30.406	38.477	-30.410	1005	958	400
St139	Ferradura	05/09/2024	15:13	15:57	38.241	-30.416	38.240	-30.420	956	942	420
St140	Ferradura	05/09/2024	18:14	19:10	38.165	-30.470	38.168	-30.475	759	724	460
St141	Ferradura	06/09/2024	08:21	09:27	38.177	-30.435	38.179	-30.444	801	829	750
St142	Ferradura	06/09/2024	10:20	11:30	38.175	-30.415	38.173	-30.425	809	881	880
St143	Ferradura	06/09/2024	12:58	13:50	38.145	-30.353	38.144	-30.358	995	967	440
St144	Ferradura	06/09/2024	15:58	17:11	38.260	-30.279	38.265	-30.289	915	930	1020
St145	Ferradura	06/09/2024	18:17	19:07	38.241	-30.244	38.241	-30.248	1009	970	380

*Dive not valid; Azor drift-cam lost

2 MAPGES 2024 LEG 1 - EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES ON BOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO, MÓNACO RIDGE

2.1 SUMMARY OF THE LEG1 OF MAPGES 2024 ARQUIPÉLAGO CRUISE

Objective: to conduct a rapid appraisal of the deep-sea benthic communities along the Alberto do Mónaco Ridge, at the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, on board of the research vessel Arquipélago. These dives aimed to contribute to the overall goal of better understanding the composition and diversity of deep-sea benthic communities in the Azores, the distribution of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and commercial fish species and assess their environmental status.

Statistics: We performed 48 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1100 m depth, covering 28 km of the seafloor and producing 48 hours of video footage, 2.66TB of disc space.

Vessel: RV Arquipélago

Dates: 06-15 July 2024

Scientific team: Telmo Morato (Chief scientist), Guilherme Gonçalves, Marc Pladevall Vilavendrell, Rachel Lacoste, Sérgio Gomes

Figure 4. Scientific team that participated in the Leg 1 of MapGES 2024 cruise on the RV Arquipélago.

2.2 HIGHLIGHTS

- 1- During the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago, we were able to perform 48 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1100 m depth, mostly covering the deeper strata of our sampling efforts

- (600-1000 m depth). We explored about 28 km of the seafloor and produced 48 hours of video footage. This year, we performed **the farthest dive ever in the Azor drift-cam** short history, in the Espadarte seamount, about 220 nm SW of Faial Island and about 170 nm from the closest Flores Island.
- 2- On July 12th 2024, we achieved an impressive and unbelievable milestone: **the dive 1000 with the Azor drift-cam**. Back in 2018 when we started to design a low-cost system to provide us with some images of the seafloor of the Azores, we never expected that only 6 years later we would have visited all geomorphological structures shallower than 1000 m and produced one of the world's most comprehensive dataset of deep-sea benthic megafauna biodiversity distribution.
 - 3- In Espadarte seamount we **lost one complete Azor drift-cam system**. In station 16, we got entangled on several lost fishing lines and a steep wall. We could see several lost multifilament lines hanging from the wall and spent about 2 hours trying to get it free but with no success, since the umbilical broke on the hydraulic winch. This is yet another example of the volume of lost fishing lines in really steep slopes of the Azores seamounts and the impact they have in deep-sea exploration. After this unfortunate event, we cancelled the dives for the rest of the day, prepared a new set of the Azor drift-cam, and were ready to go.
 - 4- Although, the video annotations still have to be finished, it seems that we **confirmed Farpas seamount as one of the areas in the Azores with higher densities of the primnoid corals *Narella bellissima* and *Narella versluysi***. We will need a dedicated PhD student to count all these observations. In 2022, we were stunned by the impressive high abundances of the primnoid corals *Narella* spp. observed in the Farpas seamount with the NIOZ towed camera system during the iMAR Eurofleets+ cruise. It was with no surprise but with great joy that the Azor drift-cam dives confirmed that similar ridges in the Farpas seamount host similar high abundances of these species.
 - 5- Over the last years, **we were able to sight several sailfin roughsharks with the Azor drift-cam which may indicate that the species is more abundant than previously expected**. During MapGES 2024 Arquipélago cruise, we observed several sailfin roughsharks of the species *Oxynotus paradoxus*. This shark was previously perceived as very rare since it has only been observed a couple of times, and it was never caught on the bottom longline fishing in the Azores.
 - 6- The overall **biodiversity observed in Monte Alto and Monte Baixo seamounts were, in general, low**. Despite the fact that we conducted many dives in Monte Baixo seamount, we were not able to sample many steep slopes or the summits of the geomorphological structures. In most cases, the drift went around the structures or the Azor drift-cam got stopped just before the slopes. The lack of sampling on particular steep areas of Monte Baixo seamount may prevent a complete understanding of the biological diversity of this area. Therefore, the low biodiversity inference should be taken with caution.
 - 7- The “bird’s nest” glass sponge ***Pheronema carpenteri* was, likely, the most conspicuous species observed during this Leg**. *Pheronema carpenteri* was frequently seen occupying the deeper strata samples, between 650 and 1000m depth, in small to large patches over soft bottoms. Not surprisingly, this species is one of the most common records in our deep-sea biodiversity occurrence database.
 - 8- We were caught by surprise with **patches of impressive biodiversity in the deep and flat Alberto do Mónaco N area**. The expectations for the biodiversity explorations in this area were low, given the flat and deep nature of the structures. However, on a couple of rocks we observed black corals *Leiopathes expansa* with *Madrepora oculata*, Paramuricea, and *Candidella imbricata*. This latter species was also found over soft substrate reaching, for some instances, patches of high densities. In this area, we spotted the first sighting with the Azor drift-cam of a Risso’s smooth-head cf. *Alepocephalus rostratus*.

Figure 5. Location of the 48 video transects (black lines) carried out with the Azor drift-cam during Leg 1 of MapGES 2024 on-board the RV Arquipléago.

Figure 6. Screenshots taken from the footage recorded during Leg 1 of MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipléago. (a) Demosponge *Haliclona magna* together with a red colony of the “bubblegum” coral *Paragorgia johnsoni*; (b) Medium-sized colonies of the primnoid *Callogorgia verticillata*; (c) Steep slope densely colonized by a vast coral garden of *Narella versluysi* and *N. bellissima*; (d) Black-coral colony of the species *Leiopathes expansa* within a *Narella* sp. dominated community; (e) Large aggregation of *Acanthogorgia* spp. together with a high diversity of soft corals; (f) Small squid; (g) Kitefin shark *Dalatias licha* hovering along the seabed; (h) Massive demosponges *Characella pachastrelloides* displaying their usual funnel morphology; (i) Vast soft fields densely colonized by a small soft coral yet to be identified; (j) Diverse coral community dominated by *Candidella imbricata*, with lace corals, highly abundant as well; (k) Lush colony of the black-coral *Leiopathes expansa* harbouring a decapod *Sternostylus formosus*, and colonizing steep basalt outcrops; (l) First ever recorded image of the a Risso’s smooth-head cf. *Alepocephalus rostratus* with the Azor drift-cam.

2.3 CRUISE DIARY OF RV ARQUIPÉLAGO LEG 1

03-05 July 2024

The start of the first leg of the MapGES 2024 ARQ cruise suffered a delay because the RV Arquipélago was not ready. We loaded our gear on the 4th of July and tested all the Azor drift-cam structures. During the 5th of July we made the last verifications, trials and adjustments. We boarded the research vessel at around 23:30.

06 July 2024

The first day of Leg 1 of MapGES 2024 on-board the RV Arquipélago, started at 00:00 when we left Horta towards an area 70 nm south-western of Princesa Alice bank. We arrived at the first station at around 08:00, where we conducted 5 dives (St001-St005) with the Azor drift-cam between 780 m and 1,100 m depth. As in many previous years, the first deployments of the day came with some technical issues on the system. After many attempts trying to fix the error associated to the “blue screen”, we replaced the live-view cylinder for a new one. The first station started at 09:00. The reduced wind speed made some of the drifts quite challenging, resulting in a relatively small distance covered by the camera system, particularly during the first dives.

Most of the areas explored were flat and usually sedimentary with sparse basaltic boulders, hosting occasional megabenthic fauna. Apart from some glass sponges such as *Aphrocallistes beatrix*, *Asconema fristedti* and *Regadrella phoenix*, patches of the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula* and solitary scleractinians *Leptopsammia formosa* were also seen colonizing the flat rock bottoms. The deepest sectors explored also contained other benthic species such as the hydrocoral *Errina atlantica* and the gorgoninans *Hemicorallium tricolor*, *Chrysogorgia* sp and *Candidella imbricata*, with the latter forming vast aggregations. Also noteworthy were the large glass sponges *Chonellasma* sp., *Hertwigia falcifera* and *Poecillastra compressa* recorded at around 900 m depth. The motile fauna observed at these depths included some eel-like fishes such as *Synaphobranchus kaupii*, *Trachyscorpia cristulata* and the first recorded image with the Azor-drift cam of a black scabbardfish *Aphanopus* sp. The shallowest dive of the day was performed over the flat top of a seamount, which was characterized by an interesting benthic community clearly dominated by the whip-coral *Narella versluysi* and where most of the other species observed at greater depths could also be seen in large numbers during this dive. The “bird’s nest” sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* was also recorded forming occasional patches. In the last dive of the day, we attempted to explore a slope at around 1100m depth, but we ran out of umbilical before reaching the seabed. We spent around 40 minutes drifting in the water column and waiting until the drift would bring us to shallower sections of the hill. After briefly reaching seafloor, we decided to end the dive and bring the system to surface, finishing the first day of the cruise at around 19:45. We started our transit to Monte Alto seamount.

Figure 7. Bathymetric map showing the five dives conducted on the first day of Leg 1 of MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Princesa Alice SW

Figure 8. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded during day 1 of Leg 1 of MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the SW Princesa Alice

07 July 2024

After having transited towards Monte Alto area during the night, we arrived at the northern-most part of the seamount, where we began our first dive at around 08:00. We successfully completed 6 dives (St006, St011), covering a depth range between 580 and 1100 m. The wind speed was a bit higher than the previous day, which resulted in better drifts during the morning dives, but with the afternoon ones becoming more challenging in terms of navigation. We experienced some technical issues, with the electric cable broken after being stuck on the winch during the 5th dive of the day (St010). However, we were able to fix it promptly and resumed the dive some minutes later. The shallower sectors between 600 m and 700 m depth were usually flat and more sedimentary than the deepest areas explored.

Some benthic megafauna could be observed on the seabed, such as the glass sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* in occasional patches, and demosponges such as *Macandrewia azorica* and *Stylocordilla pellita*. Small colonies of the gorgonian *Acanthogorgia* spp. were also visible colonizing the slope of a small hill. The decapod crab *Bathynectes maravigna* and the commercial fish *Helicolenus dactylopterus* were also recorded. The terrain was

usually steeper when we explored deeper areas of the seamount, with occasional large basalt outcrops being mostly colonized by deep-sea sponges, including *Farrea occa*, *Aphrocallistes beatrix*, *Desmacella grimaldii*, *Hertwigia falcifera* and smaller encrusting species. We also spotted very sporadic gorgonians such as *Hemicorallium tricolor* and *Hemicorallium niobe* and the black corals *Leiopathes expansa* hidden under rocky overhangs and *Bathypathes* sp. Still, large portions of the seabed were characterized by unconsolidated substrate (sand or coral rubble deposits) generally poor in terms of benthic fauna, with the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* also appearing in low abundances near these depths. Motile fauna found at these depths included *Trachyscorpia cristulata*, *Synphobranchus kaupii*, *Neocyttus helgae*, *Dalatias licha* and *Mora moro*.

Figure 9. Bathymetric map showing the six dives conducted on the 7th of July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Monte Alto seamount.

Figure 10. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 7th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Monte Alto seamount.

08 July 2024

On the 3rd day of the cruise, the weather conditions worsened as we transited towards Espadarte seamount, with wind speed reaching 20-30 knots and with the swell increasing considerably. Despite this, we managed to conduct 5 successful dives (St012-St016), exploring areas between 950 m and 600 m depth, and one

unsuccessful dive. We began the day by surveying the southern-most parts of the area, gradually moving north along the day.

The slopes explored between 900 m and 700 m contained interesting communities usually dominated by the primnoids *Narella versluysi* and *Narella bellissima*, occasionally forming large coral gardens, with big colonies of *Callogorgia verticillata* also appearing within this community. The glass sponge *Phoronema carpenteri* was frequently seen occupying the deeper sectors in sporadic patches. The shallower areas explored in Espadarte seamount also revealed interesting benthic faunal assemblages, with the “bubblegum” coral *Paragorgia johnsoni* colonizing some of the slopes, displaying its usual red and white morphotypes. Other species such as *Pleurocorallium johnsoni*, *Placogorgia* sp. and high numbers of soft corals were also among some of the fauna observed. Massive sponges likely from the species *Haliclona magna* and *Petrosia crassa* were quite frequent too. It is also noteworthy the poor conditions in which many of the coral colonies were observed, possibly showing strong signs of impacts. The primnoid *Callogorgia verticillata* was observed in higher abundances near the shallower areas explored, together with the whip-coral *Viminella flagellum*.

During station 16, we got entangled on several lost fishing lines and a steep wall. We could see several lost multifilament lines hanging from the wall. We spent about 2 hours trying to get the system free but with no success. The umbilical broke on the hydraulic winch and **we lost a complete set of the Azor drift-cam**. After this unfortunate event, we cancelled the dives for the rest of the day and started preparing a new set of the Azor drift-cam. We started transiting towards Farpas seamount.

Figure 11. Bathymetric map showing the dives conducted on the 8th of July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Espadarte seamount.

Figure 12. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 8th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Espadarte seamount.

09 July 2024

After a choppy night, we finished setting the new Azor drift-cam system and we were ready to go again. The weather didn't improve at all, and we experienced strong winds and swells during the whole day. Today, we explored the Farpas area, a seamount we had the chance to visit during the iMAR/Eurofleets+ 2022 cruise. We were able to conduct 5 successful dives (St017-St021) between 600 m and 950 m depth. The deeper strata recorded harboured benthic communities mainly composed by the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula* and its lookalike gorgonian *Chrysogorgia* sp. and by the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri*, with sporadic colonies of *Hemicorallium niobe* and *Hemicorallium tricolor*. The mora fish *Mora moro* was among some of the fishes observed at these depths, which also included *Synaphobranchus kaupii*, other eel-like fishes, and a sailfin roughshark *Oxynotus paradoxus*. As the day progressed, we started to explore shallower tops and ridges that compose the Farpas seamount. We were in close proximity of the location of a dive we performed in 2022 with the iMAR/Eurofleets+ cruise, during which we witnessed possibly the largest and densest aggregation of the primnoid corals *Narella versluysi* and *Narella bellissima* recorded in the Azores so far.

We were curious as to whether we would find the same community in other ridges of Farpas. Interestingly, we found the same abundances at a distance of ~4 nautical miles from the ridge we had previously explored, raising the question of why the ridge that was closest (1.5 nm), did not display the same biodiversity. This was undoubtedly the highlight of the day, with the coral garden extending for several hundreds of meters along

both sides of the slope explored. The abundances of the primnoid corals *N. versluysi* and *N. bellissima* frequently surpassed 10 colonies per m², with many other species present as well, such as the black corals *Leiopathes expansa* and *Parantipathes hirondele* and gorgonians that included *Acanthogorgia* spp. and *Callogorgia verticillata*. The demosponges *Haliclona magna* and *Characella pachastrelloides* were also among the benthic fauna observed. In terms of motile fauna, a juvenile sixgill shark *Hexanchus griseus*, a kitefin shark and a monk fish *Lophius piscatorius* were also recorded. The shallower hills explored contained interesting faunal assemblages, with large colonies of *Callogorgia verticillata* and the whip-coral *Viminella flagellum* colonizing the hard substrate. After the last dive, we performed the usual maintenance of the Azor drift-cam and started transition to the next area of explorations.

Figure 13. Bathymetric map showing the five dives conducted on the 9th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Farpas seamount.

Figure 14. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 9th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Farpas seamount.

10 July 2024

We arrived early in the morning at the Monte Alto SE area to begin its deep-sea exploration with the Azor drift-cam. The weather conditions improved considerably during the night, which made our work a little easier.

Throughout the day, we conducted 4 successful dives (St022-St025) in Monte Alto SE and 1 (St026) in the Monte Alto that covered a depth range between 1000 m and 650 m. With the help of the Arquipélago crew, we managed to adjust some of the initial unexpected drifts towards upslope terrain. But as the wind weakened throughout the day, the direction of the drifts changed, making the dive planning a little trickier.

The deeper strata contained little benthic diversity with occasional basalt walls hosting a few encrusting sponges, hexactinellids and unidentified demosponges of relatively large sizes. A few glass sponges *Pheronema carpenteri* were seen colonizing the flatter and deeper areas. Only when we began exploring shallower and steeper terrain, we started to see some interesting fauna, including a large wreckfish *Polyprion americanus* that circled our cameras multiple times along the transect, a kitefin shark and some decapods including *Chaceon affinis*, all at the same depth of ~800 m. Most of the slopes explored were pretty barren in terms of benthic fauna, but as we reached the top of a hill, we recorded a large coral garden dominated by *Acanthogorgia* spp., that covered both sides of its top. This community also included other species, mainly soft corals. At around similar depths but in a smaller seamount further to the East, we also observed an interesting benthic community dominated by tall colonies of the primnoid coral *Callogorgia verticillata*, concomitant with other corals such as *Narella versluysi* and *Acanthogorgia* spp. Sponges were also observed around the base and slopes of this seamount, including occasional patches of *Pheronema carpenteri*. The last dive ended at around 18:45, too late for making the 6th dive of the day. After dinner we started transiting towards the Monte de Baixo seamount.

Figure 15. Bathymetric map showing the five dives conducted on the 10th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Monte Alto SE and Monte Alto areas.

Figure 16. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 10th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Monte Alto SE and Monte Alto areas.

11 July 2024

We spent the night drifting over Monte Baixo and started the preparation of the Azor drift-cam at around 07:30. After checking the direction of the drift, we positioned the vessel and started the first dive at round 08:00. We performed 7 transects (St027-St033) between 1000 m and 600 m depth. Most of the morning drifts went smoothly and as expected, with only a few vessel adjustments needed to correct its direction. The afternoon dives were, in general, challenging due to the opposite directions of the wind and the tidal currents.

Overall, we drifted over soft and unconsolidated substrate with relatively low benthic fauna recorded in all strata explored. We began exploring the western-most part of the seamount, where separate communities dominated by *Narella* spp. and *Acanthogorgia* spp. were recorded in different dives at around the same depths (600 m – 700 m), as well as occasional *Callogorgia verticillata* and massive sponges *Characella pachastrelloides*. We also observed a small aggregation of the “lollipop” sponge *Stylocordilla pellita* covering parts of a slope, together with the lamellate sponge *Desmacella grimaldii*. The greater depths explored were characterized by sandy bottoms with little benthic fauna, but many eel-like fishes such as *Synaphobranchus kaupii* and several small deep-sea sharks, including the kitefin shark *Dalatias licha*, *Etmopterus* sp., and *Daenia* sp. Low densities of solitary scleractinians *Leptopsammia formosa*, and frequent occurrences of *Regadrella phoenix* and *Asconema fristedti* composed most of the benthic assemblage colonizing soft and mixed substrate at these greater depths. At around 950 m we encountered large and dense patches of the bird’s nest *Pheronema*

carpenteri, many of which seemed dead or in poor condition. We also found an interesting sandy field colonized by the pedunculated glass sponge *Hyalonema thomsonis*. During the day, we also observed some shrimp *Aristaeopsis edwardsiana*, some crabs *Chaceon affinis*, and some deep-sea fishes, such as *Hoplostethus mediterraneus*, *Chaunax pictus*, among other. After dinner, we finished all the desk work and left the boat drifting until the next day.

Figure 17. Bathymetric map showing the seven dives conducted on the 11th of July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Monte Baixo seamount.

Figure 18. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 11th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Monte Baixo seamount.

12 July 2024

After drifting during the night in Monte Alto seamount, we checked the direction of the drift at around 07:30. After checking the equipment and having breakfast, we positioned the vessel and started the five dives (St034-St038) of the day at 07:55. The top of this seamount revealed to be mostly flat and sedimentary, with little benthic fauna present. We tried to explore the steeper hills, but the drifts moved to unexpected directions, leading the system towards sandy and downhill terrain, with no visible benthic fauna. This happened again in some dives during the day, where strong bottom currents or shifts in wind direction made the drifts highly unpredictable and rendering the navigation of the Azor drift-cam particularly difficult.

Despite these difficulties, some of the dives went smoothly and towards upslope sectors, where large basalt outcrops harboured essentially encrusting sponges and some massive *Characella pachastrelloides*. At the base of these outcrops, large soft fields of *Pheronema carpenteri* were frequently observed. We also recorded a kitefin shark *Dalatias licha*, several birdbeak dogfish *Deania* sp., and mora fish *Mora moro*. Despite the fact that we conducted eleven dives in Monte Baixo seamount, we were not able to sample many steep slopes or the summits of the geomorphological structures. In most cases, the drift went around the structures or the Azor drift-cam got stopped just before the slopes. **The lack of sampling on particular steep areas of Monte Baixo seamount may prevent a complete understanding of the biological diversity of this area.** Nevertheless, it is likely that the overall biodiversity in this seamount is low, but this inference should be taken with caution.

We finished the day by performing one last dive in the southwest tip of Voador seamount, starting at around 1100 m depth and reaching 900 m depth. In this dive, we observed basalt outcrops with occasional bamboo corals and small glass sponges colonizing the substrate. **With this dive we achieved an impressive and unbelievable milestone: the dive 1000 with the Azor drift-cam.** Back in 2018 when we started designing a low-cost system to provide us with some images of the seafloor of the Azores, we never expected that only 6 years later we have visited all geomorphological structures shallower than 1000 m and produced one of the world's most comprehensive dataset of deep-sea benthic megafauna biodiversity distribution.

Figure 19. Bathymetric map showing the five dives conducted on the 12th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Monte Baixo seamount.

Figure 20. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 12th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in the Monte Baixo seamount.

13 July 2024

We spent the night drifting in Voador seamount, near the spot we planned to start the first dive of the day. The wind speed increased during the night, making drifts more predictable and consistent than the day before. Given the fact that this seamount was already relatively well explored, our plan was to complete some areas spread along the structure, starting in the eastern-most parts of the seamount and transiting towards the west. We spent some time in transit in between stations, making this day a little less efficient. Nevertheless, we were able to complete 5 dives (St039-St043) between 1050 m and 260 m depth. This structure seemed to contain richer benthic communities than the previously explored Monte Baixo and Monte Alto seamounts.

In the shallower areas of the seamount, we encountered many massive *Characella pachastrelloides* and *Geodia* sp. attached to rocky basalts, and some whip-corals *Viminella flagellum*. Several bluemouth rockfish *Helicolenus dactylopterus* were spotted, with one skate *Dipturus oxyrinchus*, and one sixgill shark *Hexanchus griseus*. The shallowest top of this area revealed mostly sandy substrate **densely colonized by a small soft coral yet to be identified**. Several fish species were observed near this area, including conger eel *Conger conger* and offshore rockfish *Pontinus khulii*. Several lost fishing lines laying on the seafloor were detected in the shallower depths. In the deepest strata, we recorded large fields of the glass sponge *Hyalonema thomsonis* on soft substrate, together with some patches of *Pheronema carpenteri*. On the second to last dive, we experienced some issues with the live-view feed, losing signal during the transect. We had to cut the dive short but managed to detect

the origin of the problem and fixed the electrical. While solving this problem, we switched the umbilical by a spare one and started a new dive in the same location. In less than one hour since the previous dive was aborted, we were back on the bottom performing the last dive of the day, which finished at 19:00. We transited to Alberto do Mónaco N area where we spent the night drift with the wind and currents.

Figure 21. Bathymetric map showing the five dives conducted on the 13th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Voador seamount.

Figure 22. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 13th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Voador seamount.

14 July 2024

After having briefly transited to Alberto do Mónaco N area, we spent the night drifting near the bank we would explore this day. As always, after checking the drift, we relocated the vessel and started our first dive of the day at around 07:45. All dives conducted (St044, St048) were particularly deep, with a narrow depth range between 1025 m and 890 m depth. The expectations for the biodiversity in this area were low, given the flat nature of the structures we meant to visit. Since the wind speed had decreased and adding the fact that most dives were performed below the 1000 m depth, drifts became slow, inconsistent and particularly difficult to predict, making the navigation of the Azor drift-cam challenging.

In the first dive of the day, we were caught by surprise with patches of impressive diversity. On a couple of rocks, we observed black corals *Leiopathes expansa* with *Madrepora oculata*, *Paramuricea*, and *Candidella imbricata*. This latter species was also found over soft substrate reaching, for some instances, patches of high densities. Patches of *Acanella arbuscula* were found over soft bottoms. Since the drift of this dive was quite bad and unpredictable, we decided to make an extra dive in this area, but with less success in terms of the biodiversity found. During the rest of the day, we explored the other two flat tops of this area. The central top was dominated by soft sediments with *Acanella arbuscula*, *Chrysogorgya* sp., and glass sponges such as *Regadrella phoenix* and *Hertwigia falcifera*. We spotted several eel-like fishes and the first sighting with the Azor drift-cam of a Risso's smooth-head cf. *Alepocephalus rostratus*. On the northern-most top of this seamount, we were able to perform two last dives. In one of them we witnessed an astonishing dense coral garden composed by *Candidella imbricata* in and many other coral species, including *Acanella arbuscula*, *Hemicorallium nioibe*, *Hemicorallium tricolorl*, and some colonies likely belonging to the family Paramuriceidae. This vast aggregation extended for most of the flat rock bottoms, along with solitary stony corals *Leptopsammia formosa*. Several sponges were also sighted during the dive, including *Asconema fristedti*, and large Hexactinellids yet to be identified. We also observed some fish species, such as *Neocyttus helgae* and *Trachyscorpia cristulata*.

Surprisingly, we were informed by the captain that we had to cancel the cruise because of shortage of supplies. We made it clear that the scientific crew could adapt to any type of meals that could offer a solution to keep working on the last day of the cruise. We offered other multiple solutions, including moving closer to shore so we could work within quick reach from the harbour. Unfortunately, our arguments were not convincing, and the captain kept his decision of cancelling the cruise, once again, on a Sunday evening. Without any other option, we started transiting back to Horta at around 19:35 and missed the last day of work on this Leg.

Figure 23. Bathymetric map showing the five dives conducted on the 14th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Alberto do Mónaco N area.

Figure 24. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 14th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Alberto do Mónaco N area.

15 July 2024

We arrived at Horta harbour at about 06:00, after having the cruise cancelled because of shortage of supplies. We left the RV Arquipélago at 08:00 with all the gear organized for the next leg.

3 MAPGES 2024 LEG 2 - EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES ON BOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO, PRINCESA ALICE BANK

3.1 SUMMARY OF THE MAPGES 2024 ARQUIPÉLAGO CRUISE LEG 2

Objective: to conduct a rapid appraisal of the deep-sea benthic communities dwelling on the Princesa Alice bank and adjacent areas on board of the research vessel Arquipélago. These dives aimed to contribute to the overall goal of better understanding the composition and diversity of deep-sea benthic communities in the Azores, the distribution of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and commercial fish species and assess their environmental status.

Statistics: We performed 33 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1016 m depth, covering 22 km of the seafloor and producing 29:00 hours of video footage, 1.84TB of disc space.

Vessel: RV Arquipélago

Dates: 17 - 31 July 2024

Scientific team: Carlos Dominguez-Carrió (Chief scientist), Luís Rodrigues, Manuela Ramos, Gabriela Cardoso, Marina Navarro Engesser

Figure 25. Scientific team and crew of RV Arquipélago that participated in the Leg 2 of MapGES 2024 cruise.

3.2 HIGHLIGHTS

- 1- During the Leg2 of MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago, we performed 33 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1100 m depth, mostly aiming to cover the deeper strata of the sampling area (600-1000 m depth). We explored 22 km of the seafloor and produced 29:00 hours of video footage. This leg allowed us to further explore the Princesa Alice bank and some of its adjacent areas, considered one of the most important fishing grounds of the Azores.
- 2- The **areas explored were in most cases dominated by sponge species**, with a large number of demosponges on the shallowest areas (e.g., *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, *Petrosia crassa*, *Leiodermatium pffeifferae*, *Characella pachastrelloides*) and aggregations of glass sponges on the deepest, including *Pheronema carpenteri* and *Asconema fristedti*.
- 3- **The area showed a high number of abandoned fishing lines**, which can be directly related to the high fishing effort that the Princesa Alice bank has suffered during the past decades.

Figure 26. Location of the 33 video transects (black lines) carried out with the Azor drift-cam during Leg 2 of MapGES 2024 on-board the RV Arquipélago.

Figure 27. Screenshots taken from the footage recorded during Leg 2 of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago. (a) Demosponges recorded on the shallower sectors explored. (b) Large *Leiodermatium* sponge on the rocky substrates of Princesa Alice. (c) Several *Callogorgia verticillata* colonies in association with demosponges on the shallow part of Princesa Alice. (d) A deep-sea shark *Daenia cf. profundorum* (e) One of the largest *Leiopathes glaberrima* colonies registered during MapGES 2024 cruise. (f) Several colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa* in one of the deepest dives in Princesa Alice. (g) Aggregation of the glass sponge *Asconema fristedti* on hard substrates. (h) A longline entangled on a large black coral on a vertical wall, recorded during an entanglement of the Azor drift-cam. (i) Remnants of abandoned fishing lines around sponges on mixed bottoms. (j) Coral garden with the primnoid *Narella bellissima* accompanied by the glass sponge *Asconema fristedti*. (k) Large aggregation with high densities of the glass sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* on flat bottoms of Princesa Alice. (l) A large colony of the black coral from the genus *Bathypathes* sp., not frequently observed during MapGES 2024.

3.3 CRUISE DIARY OF RV ARQUIPÉLAGO LEG 2

17 July 2024

During the 4th annual Marine Robotics Summer School (organized by the Institute of Marine Sciences – Okeanos and MIT Portugal), which took place from 8th to 19th July at Faial Island, our group participated by giving a lecture on the concept and the rationale that guided the development of the Azor drift-cam. The lecture was then complemented with practical session aboard the RV Arquipélago, which consisted of a crash-course on how to operate the system from a small vessel to obtain high-resolution underwater video images of deep-sea habitats. The summer school received 24 students from MIT and Portuguese universities with a strong interest in marine robotics and oceanography, and especially in ocean observation, marine ecology, and mapping of ecosystems. The students were divided in two groups and had the opportunity to perform one dive each with the Azor drift-

cam in the Mont'Anna seamount, in the Pico-Faial channel. The two dives completed during the practical sessions of the Marine Robotics Summer School (St049-St50) were considered valid and were added to the list of MapGES 2024 stations.

Figure 28. Bathymetric map showing the two dives conducted during the practical sessions of the Marine Robotics Summer School on the 17th July aboard the RV Arquipélago in Mont'Anna seamount, in the canal Pico-Faial.

Figure 29. Images taken during the practical session given on board of RV Arquipélago for the Marine Robotics summer school on 17th July, just before the team left for the beginning of leg 2 of the MapGES 2024 cruise.

18 July 2024

The day started with a team meeting to discuss the details of the survey among all team members that would join this second leg. We then loaded all equipment on board of RV Arquipélago just before the vessel was refuelled. All the team had boarded the vessel before 23:30 so we could leave port at midnight.

19 July 2024

We left Horta at midnight and headed towards Princesa Alice SE, where we arrived early in the morning. We started the first deployment just after 8:00 and managed to perform a total of 6 dives (St051- St056) between 340 and 840 m depth. The sea conditions were really good, with just a gentle breeze. In some cases, the drift of the vessel did not go exactly in the desired direction, with the boat moving relatively slow.

The first three dives had poor biodiversity, and the seabed was characterized by a mixture of soft and hard sediments, with some basaltic rocky outcrops observed. On the upper slopes, sponges were predominant with scattered occurrences of *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, *Petrosia crassa*, *Leiodermatium pffeiferae*, *Characella pachastrelloides* species complex, and several encrusting sponges. Also, echinoderms such as *Echinus melo* were frequently observed. The mobile fauna was characterised by *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Laemonena yarrellii*, *Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis*, and schools of *Trachurus picturatus*. In deeper areas, the sea urchins *Cidaris cidaris* and purple crinoids were commonly observed in soft bottoms. Solitary *Parantipathes hironelle* and scattered occurrences of *Flabellum sp.* were also present in sedimentary substrates. The hexactinellids *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Regadrella phoenix* and *Asconema fristedti* were common in areas with consolidated substrates, especially in basaltic rocks. In some areas *P. carpenteri* showed high densities forming clusters with several individuals, with the largest aggregations observed in sedimentary rocks. In hard substrates, the scleractinian *Leptopsammia formosa* was the most frequent coral species. Fish fauna was characterized by anguilliformes *Synaphobranchus kaupii*, few macrourids, few *Chaunax sp.*, and one elasmobranch cf. *Galeus murinus*. Aggregations of *Hoplostethus mediterraneus* were spotted at these depths. A noticeable amount of fishing lines and other types of litter was observed, especially during the fourth dive. The last dive had no lasers present on screen because the casing was accidentally moved, slightly changing its angle with respect to the camera. Once the issue was detected, the angle was fixed. We finished the last at around 19:30. After dinner, we planned the dives of the next two days to maximize the areas surveyed.

Figure 30. Bathymetric map showing the six dives conducted on the 19th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice SE area.

Figure 31. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 19th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice SE area.

20 July 2024

Another sunny working day started at 07:30, in which we performed 6 dives (St057- St062) between 320 and 870 m depth. All dives were at Princesa Alice SE, as in the day before, except for dive four, which fall inside Princesa Alice area. The day ended with some problems due to entanglements and other technical issues, but we managed to get the system back to the vessel in good condition in all cases. During the third deployment, the live-view feed stopped working halfway through the dive due to some internal breakage of the electric cable. This situation made the dive end earlier than planned, and unfortunately the issue with the cable could not be resolved on board. Fishing lines lying flat over the sediment could be observed in most dives, which did not represent a problem for the exploratory work we were doing. However, a difficult navigation during the fourth dive turned out to be a potential entanglement in a fishing line, with the umbilical opening as the boat drifted. Luckily, we managed to get the drift-cam released without further complications and bring it back to surface. When the system arrived on board, we realized that water had gotten into one of the cylinders of the concentric LED lights, causing the LEDs and the voltage regulator inside to burn down and damaged the battery. Finally, during the fifth dive, and while uphill on a vertical wall full of fishing lines, the system got stuck again in one or various lines. Thanks to the work done by the crew on the winch, we managed to retrieve the drift-cam without any damage other than an LED strip pushed down. The system even arrived with one of the fishing lines entangled around it, which got stuck on the metallic structure. When visualizing the images afterwards, we saw a large black coral *Leiopathes glaberrima* entangled on the fishing line where the system got caught.

Regarding the fauna, the deepest areas were characterized by soft bottoms hosting few species, including the scleractinian *Flabellum sp.*, a few cerianthids and the foraminifera *Syringamina fragilissima*. Patching the hard sedimentary rocks, *Pheronema carpenteri* and *Leptopsammia formosa* were observed. In volcanic rocky outcrops, the lithistids *N. nolitangerea* and *Neoschramniela sp.* were dominant, together with few occurrences of haplosclerids, such as *Petrosia sp.* and *Haliclona implexa*. At intermediate depths, hard substrates with high slopes hosted large sponges such as *Geodia sp.* and *C. pachastrelloides* species complex. At intermediate depths, an aggregation of the vase glass sponge *Asconema fristedti* was found, with very large and tall organisms. On the upper slopes, *Petrosia crassa* and *N. nolitangerea* were abundant in rocky outcrops. Over the soft bottoms, several *Oceanapia sp.* were noticed. Cnidarians abundance and diversity was low, with only some *Callogorgia verticillata* and *Viminella flagellum*, with *C. verticillata* observed as very abundant in a few spots. The dominant ichthyofauna observed at these depths were several schools of *Hoplostethus mediterraneus* and *Capros aper*. We finished the work at the same time as the day before and headed towards the shallow parts of Princesa Alice to begin the dives of the next day.

Figure 32. Bathymetric map showing the six dives conducted on the 20th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice SE area.

Figure 33. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 20th July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice SE area.

21 July 2024

Another day began with calm seas, allowing us to conduct a total of 6 dives (St063-St068) in Princesa Alice at depths ranging from 345 to 990 meters. Overall, we encountered few technical issues; however, we did notice a decrease in image quality in the bottom-right corner of the live-view camera. This was due to a malfunctioning LED board from the concentric lights, but fortunately, the overall image quality remained largely unaffected. Given that some dives reached significant depths, navigation proved to be somewhat challenging at times, necessitating a few adjustments by the vessel to optimize the system's drift direction.

Some rocky outcrops were patched by large *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, *Characella* spp., and several *Callogorgia verticillata*. In shallower slopes, few *Viminella flagellum* and *Acanthogorgia* spp. were noticed. At intermediate depths, the hexactinellids *Asconema fristedti*, *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Regadrella phoenix* and the primnoid *Narella bellissima* were frequent. Other taxa, such as the echinoderm *Echinus melo*, solitary octopus and hydrozoans were observed in the mixed substrates. Steeper outcrops had large sponges such as *Geodia* spp., *Characella pachastrelloides* and *Petrosia* spp. as well as several encrusting sponges. At greater depths (>900 m), large coral rubble accumulations with some associated fauna were noticed, including a few solitary polyps of *Leptopsammia formosa*, *Errina atlantica*, *Chrysogorgia* sp., and soft corals of the family Nephteidae. Other taxonomic groups were also observed such as *Cidaris cidaris* and purple crinoids, and a few crabs of the species *Paromola cuvieri*. In exposed rocks, several large specimens of the black corals *Leiopathes expansa* and one big *Bathypathes* sp. were observed, surrounded by other taxa, such as *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Farrea occa*, *Aphrocallistes beatrix*, dead and alive accretions of stylasterids, and also *Leptopsammia formosa*. Great densities of *Pheronema carpenteri* were also reported. Schools of *Capros aper* were observed on the upper slopes, with *Synaphobranchus* sp. and *Hoplostethus mediterraneus* more common in deeper areas, and a few *Trachyscorpia cristulata* and *Chaunax* spp. laying over coral rubble. We ended the last dive around 19:30, did some maintenance of the material and worked on the planning of the next couple of days.

Figure 34. Bathymetric map showing the six dives conducted on the 21st July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice area.

Figure 35. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 21st July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice area.

22 July 2024

The day started with glassy waters, in one of the calmest days at sea of the whole cruise. We performed a total of 6 dives (St069-St074) between 130 and 915 m depth in Princesa Alice, with the last dive on its shallowest part. This last dive filmed mesophotic habitats, with the seafloor receiving sunlight and displaying a mixture of hard and soft substrates mostly covered by algae. As in other dives, numerous fishing lines could be seen even at shallow depths. No technical issues were reported besides the remaining LED board from the concentric light burning down, which meant that the light had to be replaced for a fully functional one.

On the deepest stations, the benthic fauna presented poor diversity and low abundances, mainly with sedimentary bottoms showing few sea urchins (*Echinothuriidae*, *Cidaris cidaris*), purple crinoids and foraminiferans of the species *Syringamina fragilissima*. Hard substrates were sparsely colonized with *Leptosammia formosa*, *Bathypathes* sp., *Pliobothrus symmetricus* and *Regadrella phoenix*. Hard substrates at intermediate depths were often densely patched with massive sponges of the species *Petrosia crassa*, *Characella pachastrelloides*, *Neophrissospongia nolitangerei*, and *Leiodermatium* spp. This area showed a high diversity of Porifera species, with several sponges non-identifiable at naked eye due to their small size, some others were recognizable, such as *Phlyctaenopora bitorquis*, *Petrosia* spp. or *Haliclona implexa*. Large soft bottoms presented high abundances of *Lytocarpia myriophyllum*, but in other sedimentary areas, the lollipop sponge *Stylocordila pellita* was also present. Regarding mobile fauna, one solitary *Gephyroberyx darwinii* and a

few *Helicolenus dactylopterus* were observed, as well as schools of *Capros aper* and *Trachurus picturatus*. The shallowest dive, performed in mesophotic areas at the seamount peak, had rocky outcrops and boulders, densely patched with calcareous rodophyts, with white sponges covering the hard substrates. The most abundant echinoderm was *Centrostephanus longispinus* and some Asteroidea species. The mobile fauna was composed of *Serranus atricauda*, *Anthias anthias*, *Bodianus scrofa*, and *Scorpaena* sp. Besides the benthic fauna, the day allowed us to get spectacular views of the glassy surface of the sea, with manta rays, Portuguese man-of-war, dolphins and a red setting sun to be enjoyed until the sun disappeared over the horizon.

Figure 36. Bathymetric map showing the six dives conducted on the 22nd July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice area.

Figure 37. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 22nd July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice area.

23 July 2024

We experienced another day of very calm seas, during which we completed four additional dives (St075-St078) in Princesa Alice S at depths ranging from 450 to 1,015 meters. Overall, we encountered few technical issues, aside from minor problems with the LED strips and lasers prior to the third dive, which were resolved by replacing a faulty battery connection. Unfortunately, we had to end the fourth dive earlier than planned due to a loud noise coming from the vessel's hydraulic system. The crew instructed us to bring the system to the surface to prevent any further complications. It was later determined that the noise was caused by an oil leak, which will need to be repaired back in Faial. We departed from the last dive station at 17:00 and made our way to Horta, where we arrived just after midnight.

Communities observed on the upper slopes at Princesa Alice were predominantly dominated by sponges, including several massive species such as *Characella pachastrelloides* complex in multiple shapes (vase, tubular, lamellar and irregular amorph), *Stryphnus* sp. and *Nethea amygdaloides*. Other species were sometimes difficult to differentiate, although present in great abundances, as many lithistids like *Neophryssospongia nolitangere*, *Macandrewia azorica* and other *Petrosia* spp. Some were solitary, as large *Geodia* sp., or the vase-like *Asconema fristedti*. Some were small, such as *Stylocordyla pellita* and the repent *Xestospongia variabilis*, sometimes observed in great numbers. Sponge diversity was further increased by the large number of incrusting sponges covering the hard substrates of the summit and upper slopes. The most common corals found at these areas were *Viminella flagellum*, a few *Acanthorgorgia* spp., the soft coral Nephteidae and the lace coral *Errina dabney*. Over the soft bottoms, *Flabellum* spp. and *Cerianthus* sp. were sparsely found. Other taxa, such as the *Echinus melo*, *Paramola cuvieri*, *Chaceon affinis* and *Anamathia rissoana* were the mobile invertebrates associated to these ecosystems. The ichthyofauna observed during the shallowest dives was mainly composed of *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Laemonema* sp., *Coelorinchus* sp. and *Pagellus bogaraveo*. The deepest sectors (approx. 1000 m depth) were mainly composed of *Pheronema carpenteri* occurring in clusters, as well as other hexactinellids such as *Farrea occa*, *Regadrella phoenix*, *Aphrocallistes beatrix*. Other massive sponges were also observed, such as *Characella* sp., *Stryphnus* sp., *Petrosia* sp., *Leiodermatium* sp., and *Geodia* sp. The most characteristic anthozoan species was the coralliid *Hemicorallium niobe*, the scleractinians *Leptopsammia formosa* and *Deltocyathus moseley*. Some areas presented *Narella bellissima* and *N. versluysi* in great abundances, with mobile species such as *Synaphobranchus kaupii*, *Chaunax pictus* and the crab *Bathynectes maravigna*.

Figure 38. Bathymetric map showing the four dives conducted on the 23rd July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice S area.

Figure 39. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 23rd July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice S area.

24-29 July 2024

Problems with the vessel's hydraulic system prevented the continuation of our deep-sea explorations in the Princesa Alice area. While the engineers were trying to solve the technical problems, the scientific team performed some maintenance of the equipment, organization of the data and worked on the cruise report.

30 July 2024

The hydraulic system got repaired during the day. We departed Horta at 00:00 and set headed to Princesa Alice to continue our survey. However, during the journey, the sea conditions deteriorated rapidly, with large waves striking the boat from the side, making navigation extremely challenging. Given the circumstances, we made the decision to return to land at 4:00 AM. We arrived back in Horta at 8:30 AM and spent the rest of the day there, waiting for the sea conditions to improve.

31 July 2024

Due to the wind conditions, we decided to wait until 07:30 in the morning to depart from Horta harbour. We performed 3 dives (St079-St081) between 465 and 950 m depth. We first headed to Agulhas 12 nm to perform the first dives of the day to save some navigation time, knowing that the sea was rougher further south. Our plan was to complete 2 to 3 dives in this area while monitoring conditions before proceeding south. We started the first dive at around 10:00, with good drift that allowed us to get one hour of good seabed images. The following two dives were conducted a few miles southeast, in deeper areas. The drift was still good, and we managed to get good images from the seabed. Unfortunately, during the third dive, we encountered another issue with the hydraulic system, this time related to overheating. Since the problem could not be resolved at sea, the crew determined that we needed to have it checked in Horta by a specialist. Regrettably, this marked the last day of leg 2 of the cruise, as the required repairs necessitated flying a technician from Lisbon. Consequently, the cruise was put on hold until the hydraulic system could be fixed.

Regarding the fauna observed in the 3 dives done, it was similar to the previous days. The upper bathyal was characterised by scattered occurrences of massive sponges, such as *Characella pachastrelloides* complex, *Petrosia crassa*, *Spongosorites* sp. and *Geodia* sp. Smaller and undetermined encrusting sponges were very abundant all over the mixed substrates. The lower bathyal areas presented not only large sedimentary areas with few organisms (such as the foraminifera *Syringamina fragilissima*, *Cerianthus* sp. and *Deltocyathus moseleyi*) but also large deposits with biodebitic rubble and consolidated substrates colonized by *Pheronema carpenteri* accompanied by *Candidella imbricata* and *Narella versluysi*. Also, other hexactinellids such as *Regadrella phoenix*, *Farrea occa*, *Hyalonema* sp., and the cnidarians *Errina atlantica*, *Acanella arbuscula*, *Parantipathes hidrondelle* and *Leptopsammia formosa* were observed in association to these *Pheronema* aggregations, although in lower abundances. Hard substrates formed by volcanic rocky outcrops presented high diversities, also with soft corals such as *Nephtyidae* and *Anthomastus/Pseudoantomastus* sp. and small Caryophylliids. Other associated fauna were the crab *Bathynectes maravigna* as well as some fishes: *Chaunax pictus*, *Trachyscorpia cristulata*, *Hoplostethus* cf. *atlanticus* and one elasmobranch *Dipturus oxyrinchus*.

Figure 40. Bathymetric map showing the three dives conducted on the 31st July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Agulhas 12 milhas - Açor area.

Figure 41. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 31st July of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Agulhas 12 milhas - Açor area.

1-4 August

Problems with the vessel's hydraulic system determined the cancelation of the Leg 2 of the MapGES 2024 cruise onboard the RV Arquipélago. While the engineers and vessel's crews were trying to solve the technical problems, the scientific team performed the usual tasks in such circumstances that included maintenance of the equipment, organization of the data and the preparation of the cruise report.

4 MAPGES 2024 LEG 3 - EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES ON BOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO, MAR DA PRATA BANK, D. JOÃO DE CASTRO, AND HEITOR ÁLVARES

4.1 SUMMARY OF THE LEG 3 OF MAPGES 2024 ARQUIPÉLAGO CRUISE

Objective: To conduct a rapid appraisal of the deep-sea benthic communities dwelling on the Mar da Prata bank, D. João de Castro, and Heitor Álvares seamounts on board of the research vessel Arquipélago. These dives would aim to contribute to the overall goal of better understanding the composition and diversity of deep-sea benthic communities in the Azores, the distribution of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and commercial fish species and assess their environmental status.

Vessel: RV Arquipélago

Dates: 12 August - 24 August 2024 (Cancelled)

Scientific team: João Balsa (Chief scientist), Guilherme Gonçalves, Sérgio Gomes, Gabriela Cardoso

4.2 CRUISE DIARY OF RV ARQUIPÉLAGO LEG 3

12/08/2024 – 24/08/2024

The hydraulic system on the RV Arquipélago, which had halted the progress of Leg 2, unfortunately remained unresolved for more than 20 days. During this period, the vessel was confined to Horta harbour as we awaited the arrival of a specialized technician from Lisbon. Once he arrived on the 22nd, he quickly assessed the situation and was able to repair the hydraulic system in less than one day. Throughout the waiting period, all of our gear remained securely on the vessel, and the scientific crew was fully prepared to depart at a moment's notice. Despite our readiness, the unfortunate circumstances meant that the planned activities for Leg 3 could not be executed. This included critical explorations of the Mar da Prata bank, as well as the D. João de Castro and Heitor Álvares seamounts. The inability to carry out this important work was disappointing, but we remained committed to our research objectives and looked forward to future opportunities to continue our exploration.

5 MAPGES 2024 LEG 4 - EXPLORATION AND MAPPING OF DEEP-SEA BIODIVERSITY IN THE AZORES ON BOARD THE RV ARQUIPÉLAGO, PRINCESA ALICE AND MID-ATLANTIC RIDGE

5.1 SUMMARY OF THE LEG4 OF MAPGES 2024 ARQUIPÉLAGO CRUISE

Objective: to conduct a rapid appraisal of the deep-sea benthic communities dwelling on the Princesa Alice bank and adjacent areas and on the deeper sectors the Óscar, Ferradura, and Bicuda seamounts, on board of the research vessel Arquipélago. These dives aim to contribute to the overall goal of better understanding the composition and diversity of deep-sea benthic communities in the Azores, the distribution of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) and commercial fish species and assess their environmental status.

Statistics: We performed 64 dives with the Azor drift-cam down to 1150 m depth, covering 33 km of the seafloor and producing 62 hours of video footage, 3.2 TB of disc space.

Vessel: RV Arquipélago

Dates: 24 August - 07 September 2024

Scientific team: Guilherme Gonçalves and Luís Rodrigues (Chief scientists), Gerald H. Taranto, Sérgio Gomes, Manuela Ramos, Gabriela Cardoso

Figure 42. Scientific team and crew of RV Arquipélago that participated in the Leg 4 of MapGES 2024 cruise.

5.2 HIGHLIGHTS

- 1- During the Leg4 of MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago, we were able to perform 64 dives with the Azor drift-cam, covering a wide range of depth strata (250-1050 m depth). We explored about 33 km of the seafloor and produced 62 hours of video footage.
- 2- We were able to visit two of the **most heavily fished grounds of the Azores archipelago – the Princesa Alice and Açor banks** - and their surrounding areas. Indeed, we had strategically left this large area to explore last, as we were quite aware of the danger it represents for the operation of the Azor drift-cam. Despite being subject to high degrees of fishing effort, we still uncovered interesting benthic

assemblages thriving in these areas, even those present at shallower depths, usually more heavily explored. We were able to navigate the Azor drift-cam safely along these communities even with the presence of lost longlines and fishing gear, once again proving the **effectiveness of this camera system even in the most challenging and demanding areas.**

- 3- On many occasions we were intrigued by the **conspicuous presence of a vast variety of sponges in the Princesa Alice bank** and surrounding areas such as the massives *Characella pachastrelloides*, *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, *Petrosia crassa* and *Geodia* sp., many of which attained **particularly large sizes**. Indeed, many of the benthic communities we discovered were mostly dominated by the Phylum Porifera, present across all depth strata explored. We recorded one of the **largest and densest aggregations of the hexactinellid *Pheronema carpenteri***, occupying the steep slopes and flat top of a small ridge in the Açor area.
- 4- The large flat top of the Açor S area was thought to be highly sedimentary and hosting little benthic fauna. However, as we tried to climb over the 100m tall vertical wall south of this bank, we began observing **many colonies of the endemic hydroid coral *Errina dabneyi***. At the top of the mount, a vast aggregation of **the scleractinian *Eguchipsammia cornucopia* was seen building a structural and dense reef** that hosted other coral species such as, once more, *Errina dabneyi*. Despite the Açor bank being subject to a high degree of fishing effort, we could still see **large colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes glaberrima* in Açor S area** most of which appeared to show healthy conditions. These specimens were seen colonizing the slopes of the surrounding areas of this large bank.
- 5- While exploring Ferradura seamount on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, at depths exceeding 1000 meters, we witnessed an impressive and quite unique faunal assemblage. It was characterized by a **diverse benthic community of several coral species** such as large *Paragorgia johnsoni*, *Leiopathes expansa*, *Placogorgia* sp., *Lophelia pertusa*, *Madrepora oculata*, *Hemicorallium niobe*, *H. tricolor*, *Pleurocorallium johnsoni*, and *Pseudoanthomathus* sp., revealing **MAR unique fragile and vulnerable deep-sea ecosystems**. The Ferradura seamount also hosted what could be **one of the densest aggregations of the scleractinian *Errina atlantica* recorded so far in the Azores.**
- 6- A special finding was the observation of the hexactinellid sponge *Hertwigia falcifera* which is **rarely recorded with the Azor drift-cam.**
- 7- Although in small aggregations, the presence of one of the longest-lived fish species, the **orange roughy *Hoplostethus atlanticus***, spotted at Oscar Seamount indicates the presence of this vulnerable fish stock at the MAR ecosystems.
- 8- On 6th September 2024 we achieved a significant milestone with the Azor drift-cam by conducting **our deepest dive to date**. This remarkable dive took place at Ferradura seamount, reaching an impressive depth of 1,153 meters. This achievement not only highlights the capabilities of the Azor drift-cam system but also enhances our understanding of the deep-sea environments and ecosystems present in this region. The data gathered from this dive will be invaluable for our ongoing research and conservation efforts.

Figure 43. Location of the 64 video transects (black lines) carried out with the Azor drift-cam during Leg 4 of MapGES 2024 on-board the RV Arquipélago.

Figure 44. Screenshots taken from the footage recorded during Leg 4 of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago. (a) Partially alive reef of the scleractinian *Eguchipsammia cornucopia* covering the top of a mount; (b) Vertical wall harbouring several colonies of the hydrocoral *Errina dabneyi*; (c) Large colony of the black coral *Leiopathes glaberrima* used as a refuge by a small fish; (d) Tall specimen of the primnoid coral *Callogorgia verticillata*; (e) Dense *Errina atlantica* aggregation on a biodetritic deposit of coral rubble; (f) Lamellate sponge *Desmacella grimaldii* covering the edge of rocky outcrops; (g) Vast and highly abundant soft field of the bird's nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri*; (g) Coral garden dominated by the primnoids *Narella versluyisi* and *N. bellissima*; (h) Basalt rock colonized by several colonies of *Candidella imbricata*; (i) Impressive aggregation of large colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa*; (k) Orange roughy hovering along soft sediments and (l) an elusive swordfish.

5.3 CRUISE DIARY OF RV ARQUIPÉLAGO LEG 4

24 August 2024

After finally receiving the news from the crew of the RV Arquipélago that the hydraulic system was operational once again, we were able to resume our exploration of the areas that we could not thoroughly sample during Leg 2. The original plan for Leg 4, which focused on exploring the deeper sectors of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, had to be adjusted to allow for a more comprehensive investigation of the areas initially intended for Leg 2. As a result, we prioritized returning to Princesa Alice bank and its surrounding seamounts during the first half of this leg. We left Horta harbour at around 03:30 in the morning, to arrive in time for the first dive of the Leg, in Boureé NE area, at around 08:20. We explored a depth range between 620 m and 920 m, completing 5 successful dives throughout the day (St082-St086). During the morning dives, the strong NE winds enabled relatively consistent and long drifts, directing the camera system towards the planned endpoints. However, after lunch, weather conditions changed, with the wind speed reducing a bit and shifting completely, with the bottom currents exerting higher influences on the behaviour of the camera system. During these cases, drifts were quite random, unexpected and slow.

Regarding the megabenthic fauna, we observed interesting communities in the deepest sectors, with the most conspicuous species being the primnoid coral *Candidella imbricata*, which frequently formed dense coral gardens, also composed by other species including the bamboo coral *Acanella arbuscula*, the whip-coral *Narella versluysi* and small colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes expansa*. The systerid *Errina atlantica* was also commonly observed along this community, which grew on coral rubble deposits or steep slope of consolidated sediments. The sponge communities were sparsely distributed and composed by several species of hexactinellids (e.g., *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Farrea occa*, *Aphrocallistes beatrix* and *Regadrella phoenix*). The mora fish *Mora moro*, and *Trachyscorpia cristulata* were some of the fish species recorded. In the shallowest areas, we also observed interesting faunal assemblages, particularly a large sponge-dominated community, including massive sponges *Characella pachastrelloides* complex and *Macandrewia azorica* as well as small digitate sponges (e.g., *Petrosia* spp. and *Stylocordilla pellita*). We ended the last dive of the day at around 19:00.

Figure 45. Bathymetric map showing the five dives conducted on the 24th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Boureé NE and Boureé E areas.

Figure 46. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 24th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Boureé NE and Boureé E areas.

25 August 2024

After having transited towards the first sampling spot of the day and drifting during the night, we quickly checked the direction of the drift and repositioned the vessel to the intended starting point. We set the objective of finishing the exploration of Boureé E area, this time working in the southernmost geomorphological units of the area. During the usual morning tests of the camera system, we realized we had no live view feed, with the common blue screen issue. After a brief session of intense troubleshooting, we detected its origin, which was related to the umbilical connection with the live view cylinder. We were able to start the first dive of at around 08:20. We also came across an issue with the live view feed during the third dive, losing signal for no apparent reason, but since it came back as we were recovering the system, we decided to resume the dive. We also had water leaking inside the GoPro housing, which made us discard the battery and possibly the camera itself. The fact that we had long transits between stations (on one occasion reaching 9nm) meant the workday was not as efficient as usual, but still managed to conduct 6 dives (St087 – St092) between 1055 m and 370 m depth. We faced occasional heavy rains throughout the day, making our work a little more uncomfortable. In addition to this, we were in the middle of an anticyclone, which, once again, rendered the drifts quite unpredictable and dive planning decisions particularly difficult. Despite continuous attempts from the vessel captain to better direct the transect, most efforts were either ineffective or not as intended.

The Boureé E characteristic megafauna was merely composed by sponges. The intermediate depths surveyed at around 600-700 m, presented mixed communities in transition from known deeper taxa very common at low bathyal areas, such as the hexactinellids *Pheronema carpenteri* and *Farrea occa* together with upper bathyal massive astrophorids as *Characella* spp., *Stryphnus* sp. and *Geodia* sp., lithistids *Macandrewia azorica*, *Neophrissopongia nolintangere* and haplosclerids *Haliclona magna* and *Petrosia* spp. Also patching hard substrates, several encrusting species (e.g., *P. bitorquis*) and small stipitate morphologies (e.g. *Stylocordila pellita*, *Exuperantia arquipelagus*) also increased the local diversity. Also a few cnidarians, solitary specimens of *Errina atlantica*, *Pseudoanthomastus* sp. and bryozans were spotted during the transect. At shallower areas of the upper slope presented sparse but large *Viminella flagellum* and *Callogorgia verticillata*. At lower slope, a

few specimens of *Acanthogorgia cf. armata* were observed too. However, massive sponges were the most dominant taxonomic group, with large *Characella pachastrelloides*, *Nethea amygdaloides*, *Geodia* sp., *Leiodermatium pfeifferae*, *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, and *Petrosia crassa*. Associated to this habitat, several fishes, such as the *Conger conger*, *Helicolenus dactylopterus* and *Hoplostethus mediterraneus*, were found under a mixed biodetritric substrate with rock outcrops. We ended the last dive at 19:10 and planned the next day of work and the area we would explore.

Figure 47. Bathymetric map showing the six dives conducted on the 25th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Boureé E area.

Figure 48. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 25th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Boureé E area.

26 August 2024

After spending a calm night drifting in the bank of Princesa Alice, we positioned the vessel and began the first dive of the day at around 08:00. Given the fact that most stations were performed at relatively shallow sectors (~300m), we managed to conduct a total of 7 dives (St093 – St099), with one of them being aborted due to an issue with the live view feed. We covered a narrow depth range between 240 m and 380 m. Similarly to previous days, the drifts were very hard to predict. Despite the wind speeds being strong to direct the vessel towards the intended endpoints, the bottom currents acted strongly on the camera system, changing the direction of the transect often and considerably. In addition, the wind direction changed multiple times during the day, which forced us to check the drift many times before deploying the system. Towards the end of the day, the wind picked-up considerably, which helped us massively, rendering the drifts more consistent and faster.

Communities present at the upper slope areas of the Princess Alice bank were markedly characterized by the occurrence of high densities of *Errina dabneyi* along the flattened sedimentary areas mixed with hard substrate. Other corals were observed, such as *Viminella flagellum*, *Paracalyptrophora josephinae* and *Callogorgia verticillata* but in a scattered distribution. Some large colonies of the black coral *Leiopathes glaberrima* were also recorded. The hydroids, *Plumarella* sp. and *Lytocarpia* sp. were found patching mixed substrates. Another hydroid, still to be unidentified, was found in particularly high densities along vast areas of the seabed. One large reef of *Eguchipsammia cornucopia* was found, however, most of it was dead, with a few specimens alive laying above the coral rubble. The lace coral *Errina dabneyi* was observed associated to this reef in its upper layer too. Regarding sponge communities, some large *Petrosia crassa*, *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, *Leiodermatium* spp. and *Macandrewia azorica* were very common colonizing rocky slopes. While other sponge species such as Cf. *Polymastia* sp. and the lamellate *Poecillastra compressa* and *Desmacella grimaldii* were occasionally observed. Concerning fish species, the flatfish *Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis*, the *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Pontinus kuhlii*, *Muraena helena* and schools of *Capros aper* and *Trachurus picturatus* were associated to this environment too. Some specimens of the elasmobranch *Raja clavata* (including some eggs nearby this species encounter) were spotted in soft bottoms.

Figure 49. Bathymetric map showing the seven dives conducted on the 26th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice.

Figure 50. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 26th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice.

27 August 2024

Today, we decided to explore the Princesa Alice S and W areas. We began exploring a small volcano chain in the southernmost sector of Princesa Alice S, at around 07:55. Despite having long transits between stations, we managed to conduct 6 dives (St100 – St105) across 940 m and 380 m depth. The drifts were easier to predict; however, we had to constantly check weather conditions and watch the transect line to make adjustments and reach the desired endpoints. In some cases, that goal was not achieved. No major technical issues occurred.

Faunal assemblages in the slope areas of these small mounts were generally characterized by high densities of sponges covering the rocky bottoms. The species communities at these depths exhibit consistency, with several lithistids *Leiodermatium pfeifferae*, *Macandrewia azorica*, *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, and *Exsuperantia archipelagus*, contributing to substantial coverage. Additionally, the astrophorid *Characella pachastrelloides* complex, *Nethea amygdaloides*, and *Stryphnus* sp. were quite common. The large, globular *Geodia* sp. was also frequently observed in several areas. Furthermore, petrosiids were abundant, particularly *Petrosia crassa* and the globular forms of *Petrosia* spp. The vase sponge *Asconema fristedti* and small clusters of *Sympagella nux* were the glass sponges documented. Other small sponges, including *Stylocordyla pellita*, along with various encrusting sponges such as *Hymedesmia* sp. and *Hexadella* spp., were also found in great abundance throughout the area.

Regarding cnidarians, the whip coral *Viminella flagellum* appeared in small colonies, and *Paracalyptophora josephinae* and *Callogorgia verticillata* were observed in a more scattered distribution. Flat sedimentary

bottoms with sand ripples were characterized by low megafauna diversity. We observed a small school of *Beryx decadactylus*, one large sixgill shark *Hexanchus griseus* and the birdbeak dogfish *Deania calceus*. At areas deeper than 1000 m, we observed a dense community of *Candidella imbricata* with *Pheronema carpenteri*. This community has several other associated species, such as solitary specimens of *Leiopathes expansa*, *Acanella arbuscula*, *Hemicorallium niobe* and *H. tricolor*. Areas with coral rubble of dead *Lophelia pertusa* were detected with several associated species. We ended the last dive at around 19:15.

Figure 51. Bathymetric map showing the seven dives conducted on the 27th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice S and Princesa Alice W areas.

Figure 52. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 28th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Princesa Alice S and Princesa Alice W areas.

28 August 2024

We spent the night drifting along the De Guerne area, an interesting feature East of Princesa Alice bank, which has a wide bathymetric range within a few nautical miles, allowing us to cover different depths throughout the day. We performed 7 successful dives (St106 – St112) between 920 m and 360 m depth. The drifts were slower than usual, because of low wind speeds. With the help of the captain, the vessel adjustments were, in most cases, enough to direct the transect into the desired direction. During the third dive of the day, we repeatedly came across several lost fishing lines, but luckily we did not get entangled in any. We decided to cut the dive short and recover the equipment.

During the morning, we decided to explore the shallowest tops of this feature, at around 360 m depth, where we drifted over a small community of the primnoid *Callogorgia verticillata*. Other cnidarians were observed, including *Errina dabneyi*, cf. *Plumarella* sp., and *Acanthogorgia* spp. Attached to hard substrates, under slopes with rock outcrops and vertical walls, many sponge species were recorded, including *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, *Leiodermatium pfeifferae*, *Macandrewia azorica*, *Characella pachastrelloides* and *Spongosorites* sp. Petrosiids, several globular shaped *Petrosia* spp. and the repent shaped *Xestospongia variabilis*, were very abundant too. Sedimentary deposits over flattened areas occupied large extensions of the upper bathyal. Despite the poor megafauna diversity, *Syringamina fragilissima* colonises these soft bottoms. Notwithstanding, deeper deposits of calcareous biodebris of molluscs and echinoderms dead shells occupying great areas, are place for *Cidaris cidaris* aggregations. One of the largest *Pheronema carpenleri* aggregations was observed at De Guerne mid bathyal (approx. 900 m). This assemblage is commonly monospecific, but it is often harbouring other species, such as *Asconema fristedti*, *Regadrella phoenix*, *Farrea occa* and *Stylocordyla pellita*. Dense gardens of the primnoids *Narella bellissima* and *N. versluysi*, and frequent occurrences of *Hemicorallium niobe* were found mixed with *Pheronema* beds. One cephalopod with relatively large dimensions and a *Dipturus oxyrinchus*, were some of the mobile fauna associated to the deeper environments of De Guerne.

Figure 53. Bathymetric map showing the seven dives conducted on the 28th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in De Guerne area.

Figure 54. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 28th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in De Guerne area.

29 August 2024

As we were checking the weather forecast for the next few days, we realized the wind would increase substantially from the 31st of August until 2nd of September, which meant the second half of the MapGES 2024 leg 4 with RV Arquipélago would have to be shortened for a few days. The scientific crew and the Arquipélago crew came to a compromise of extending this first half of the Leg for one more day, leaving the windy days to re-stock food supplies and to amend a few issues related with the hydraulic system. This left us with the option of staying in the Açor S and Açor banks for two days and try to cover this large area the best we could. We were particularly aware of the danger related to lost fishing gear in this bank, as it is one of the most heavily fished areas near Faial. Strategically, we began surveying the deepest sector of interest, slowly progressing towards shallower spots, where the likeliness of encountering long lines was higher. The day started at around 08:00 in a small deep hill north of Açor S area. Most drifts were predictable, allowing us to conduct 6 dives (St113 – St118) across 800 m and 390 m depth range, covering a large extension of this vast area.

The megafauna observed at Açor S was uniform along transects. Large extensions of sedimentary areas at the Açor S mounts and hills basins appear with relatively poor diversity. *Pheronema carpenteri* beds dominate the bathyal areas. These *Pheronema* meadows were frequently mixed with *Asconema fristedti* and *Macandrewia azorica*, together with the primnoids *Narella bellissima* and *N. versluysi*. Although in other sides of slope areas, *Asconema fristedti* can create also monospecific communities. At the upper slope, the sponge communities

shift to *Characella pachastrelloides*, *Leiodermatium pffeiferae*, *Neophrissospongia nolintangere*, *Macandrewia azorica* and *Petrosia crassa*. A dense, but very localized, aggregation of the stipitate sponge *Stylocordilla pellita* was also recorded within these depths. Remarkably, a few very large black corals *Leiopathes glaberrima* were recorded at upper slopes. Schools of *Beryx spp.* were observed, but the most interesting observation was of a swordfish *Xiphias gladius* filmed for the second time with the Azor drift-cam system this year.

Figure 55. Bathymetric map showing the seven dives conducted on the 29th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Açor S area.

Figure 56. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 28th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Açor S area.

30 August 2024

Today, we explored a little more of the southern slopes of Açor S area, given the fact we had only stayed in the northern-most sectors of the bank in the previous day. These slopes are known to be particularly steep, sometimes coming from 1000 m to 300 m depth in a matter of a few hundred meters of distance. We did not want to push our luck, so we selected a spot that seemed less risky, starting at 600 m depth up to 350 m. We began the first dive of the day at around 08:15. Indeed, we drifted over a very tall vertical wall, pushing the limits of the Azor drift-cam, but managing to cross it safely. After this, we transited towards Açor area, where we were able to conduct 5 more stations. In total, we performed 6 dives (St119- St124) between 850 m and 285 m depth. Strategically, we worked our way Northwards, to finish the last dive closer to shore, allowing us to extend the workday as much as we could, since we needed to come ashore before midnight.

The steep area of Açor S surveyed at the first dive of the day, was patched by a dense community of *Errina dabneyi* at the lower slope. A large deposit of dead *Errina dabneyi* rubble was observed at the slope base. At the top of the mount, after climbing a tall vertical wall, was a copious amount of dead and alive *Eguchipsammia cornucopia* building a structural reef. The reef rubble had several associated species, including more *Errina dabneyi*. Other corals, such as *Viminella flagellum*, *Paracalyptrophora josephinae*, *Callogorgia verticillata* and *Acanthogorgia* spp. composed the community established over the mixed sandy to rocky substrates of the mount summit. Some areas had several large and tall *Leiopathes glaberrima* occurrences too. Slopes were also densely covered with sponges, an assemblage composed by the *Characella pachastrelloides* of irregular shape and small size, the typical massives *Petrosia crassa*, *Macandrewia azorica* and the lamellate *Poecillastra compressa* bordering rock outcrops and on top of coral rubble. Sponge community differ slightly in some areas, where *Stylocordyla pellita*, *Asconema fristedti*, *Desmacella grimaldii* and *Petrosia* spp. were also occasionally found. Deeper areas (at approx. 900 m) presented highly dense *Pheronema carpenteri* beds, probably one of the largest aggregations ever seen in the Azores. These aggregations had other species occurring among them, such as other Hexactinellid *Regadrella phoenix* and sporadically some corals *Hemicorallium niobe* and *Acanella arbuscula*. Interestingly, at the base of the mount a large deposition of spines from the urchin *Cidaris cidaris* was observed, with some alive ones laying on it. Shallower areas presented also high sedimentary deposition with fine sandy bottoms, where tracks of mobile organisms (e.g. holothurians) could be detected. Consolidated sedimentary rock with crevices were home to several fishes (e.g. *Conger conger*, *Pontinus khuli*, and *Phycis* sp.). Some rock outcrops were also covered with *Neophrissospongia nolitangere* and some *Viminella flagellum* and hydroids cf. *Plumarella* sp. patches. We began returning to shore at 17:45, arriving in Faial close to 21:00.

Figure 57. Bathymetric map showing the seven dives conducted on the 30th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Açor S and Açor area.

Figure 58. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 28th August of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Açor S and Açor area.

01-02 September 2024

We stayed on land due to issues with the hydraulic system and a malfunctioning fridge, which needed repair. As predicted previously, the bad weather conditions of these days also forced us to stay on land, using the opportunity to refuel and re-stock food supplies of the ship.

03 September 2024

After changing some scientific crew elements, we left Horta harbour at around 00:00 and transited towards Óscar Seamount during the night. In total, we performed six dives (St125-St130) across a depth gradient between 520 m and 1080 m depth. The first station started at around 09:00.

Some hills composing the Oscar Seamount, have high sedimentation coverage with poor megafauna. Nevertheless, it was possible to find, at mixed substrates, some very large lithistids *Leiodermatium pfeifferae*. Other areas at the similar depths presented high densities of *Acanthogorgia* spp., patches of *Viminella flagellum*, *Muriceides paucituberculata*, *Anthomastus/Pseudoanthomastus* sp. and a diverse sponge fauna composed by *Geodia* sp., *Petrosia* spp., *Haliclona magna*, *Desmacella grimaldii*, *Spongosorites* sp. and several encrusting sponges. At intermediate depths, *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Regadrella phoenix* and the laminar *Poecillastra compressa* were the most abundant and frequent sponges. The primnoids *Narella bellissima*, *N.*

versluysi, *Callogorgia verticillata* and the black coral *Parantipathes hirondelle* were structuring the corals community at those depths. At deeper areas, below 1000 m, we observed some *Chrysogorgia* sp., small *Leiopathes expansa*, *Bathypathes pseudoalternata* and *Hertwigia falcifera*. The fishes observed during the dives vary from a juvenile of *Hexanchus griseus* to some benthic fishes such as *Chaunax pictus*, *Mora moro*, *Trachyscorpia cristulata* and *Helicolenus dactylopterus*. We also observed echinoderms Goniasteridae, *Peltaster* sp., *Echinus melo* and decapods *Sternostylus formosus* and *Chaceon affinis*.

Figure 59. Bathymetric map showing the six dives conducted on the 3th September of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Óscar area.

Figure 60. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 3th September of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Óscar area.

04 September 2024

We spent the night drifting over Óscar seamount and started the preparation of the Azor drift-cam at around 07:40. After checking the direction of the drift, we positioned the vessel and started the first dive at 08:00. We performed six transects (St131-St136) between 1050 m and 650 m depth.

Faunal assemblages at upper bathyal (500-600 m) were formed by great densities of *Callogorgia verticillata*, *Narella bellissima* and *Narella versluysi*. Several other species were observed in between *Narella*'s gardens, such as *Parantipathes hirondelle* and *Acanthogorgia* spp. in some areas, or *Anthomastus/Pseudoanthomasthus* sp., *Pleurocorallium johnsoni*, *Placogorgia* sp., *Muriceides paucituberculata* and *Elatopathes abietina* in other areas. These areas presented a high accumulation of coral rubble. At deeper bathyal areas (900 m), the community was composed by a few records of *Leiopathes expansa*, abundant *Narella versluysi* and some patches of *Errina atlantica* and *Hemicorallium niobe*. Several specimens of scleractineans *Vaughanella coccinea*, *Caryophyllia* sp. and *Leptopsammia formosa* were found attached to rock outcrops. Sponges were also very frequent with *Phakellia ventilabrum* aggregations and *Desmacella grimaldii* in rocky substrate. Some large specimens of sponges were found isolated, for instance a *Geodia megastrella* was recorded with a *Paramola cuvieri* associated to it. Also, a *Geodia pachydermata* and a massive *Stryphnus* sp. were found alone in sedimentary areas. In other areas at same depths, the hexactinellids *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Regadrella phoenix* and *Aphrocallistes beatrix* were frequently recorded. Also, smaller species such as *Exsuperantia archipelagus*, *Haliclona filholi* were found attached to sedimentary rock. Areas with large extensions of biogenic detritus of coral rubble and sandy silty bottoms were environments with poorer diversity, even though, some species could be depicted such as *Deltocyathus moseley*, *Syringammia fragilissima* and *Cerianthus loydii*. Unexpectedly, several specimens of orange roughly *Hoplostethus atlanticus* were detected at Oscar Seamount bathyal layers. Furthermore, other fish species such as *Hoplostethus mediterraneus*, *Neocyttus helgae*, *Chaunax pictus*, *Mora moro*, *Trachyscorpia cristulata* and the small shark *Etmopterus* sp. were spotted at deep bathyal areas too.

Figure 61. Bathymetric map showing the six dives conducted on the 4th September of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Óscar area.

Figure 62. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 4th September of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Óscar area.

05 September 2024

Today we transited to Bicuda small seamount, but the weather conditions deteriorated because of the windy conditions (15-20 knots). We conducted two dives in Bicuda seamount (St137-St138), exploring areas between 1050 m and 1000 m depth, and then we moved to Ferradura during the lunch time. After the transit to Ferradura, the afternoon started with some technical issues with the live view. The problem was solved using a spare umbilical. Unfortunately, we had live view issues again before the next deployment. It took us a while to understand that also the second electrical cable was giving its last breath. The problem was solved switching to the third and last umbilical. This situation made the dives starting two hours later than planned. Despite this, we conducted two successful dives (St139-St140), exploring areas between 1000 m and 800 m depth. The issues with the first cable that broke was solved on board, meaning that it was ready to be used in the next day.

At Bicuda seamount, the performed dives were made only at deep areas, nearly from 1050 to 1000 m depth. Faunal assemblages at these depths were characterized by the presence of corals, such as *Acanella arbuscula*, *Chrysogorgia* sp., *Parantipathes hironelle*, *Pliobothrus symmetricus*, *Hemicorallium niobe*, *Muriceides paucituberculata*, *H. tricolor* and *Vaughanella conccinea*, at hard substrates. We also observed few sponges' specimens of *Hertwigia falcifera*, *Regadrella phoenix*, *Desmacella grimaldii* and *Polymastia* sp. In contrast, at soft substrates, the echinoderm *Cidaris cidaris* was the most frequent species recorded. At the deep areas (approx. 950 m) some coral species such as *Acanella arbuscula*, *Chrysogorgia* sp., *Hemicorallium niobe* and

Errina atlantica were found. Also sponges, e.g. *Petrosia clavata* and *Desmacella grimaldii* were spotted over rock outcrops surrounded by sedimentary deposits with *Cidaris cidaris*. At intermediate depths (approx. 750 m), a coral garden of *Narella bellissima* of small size covered a large extension. Although in low abundances, black corals *Parantipathes hironelle* and *Elathopathes abietina*, as well as the sponges *Poecillastra compressa*, *Desmacella grimaldii*, *Petrosia sp.* and *Haliclona filholi* were noticed patching rock outcrops.

Figure 63. Bathymetric map showing the four dives conducted on the 5th September of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Bicuda and Ferradura areas.

Figure 64. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 5th September of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Bicuda and Ferradura area.

06 September 2024

After drifting during the night in Southwest part of Ferradura seamount, we checked the direction of the drift at around 07:50. After changing the cable and checking the equipment, we positioned the vessel and started our first dive at 08:05. We explored a depth range between 600 m and 1150 m, completing five successful dives throughout the day (St141-St145).

The geomorphological structures visited at Ferradura Bank (small ridges type) presented different assemblages or facies at intermediate to deep bathyal areas. At the western part (approx. 800 m depth), a dense *Errina atlantica* reef was found in a biodetritic deposit of coral rubble. Several other species were observed in association to *Errina* “alive reef” together with dead rubble, such as *Anthomastus/Pseudoanthomastus* sp. in great abundances, the scleractinians *Madrepora oculata* and *Leptopsammia formosa* and small *Narella versluysi*. Also, hexactinellids were associated to the *Errina* reef, the *Farrea occa* and small sized *Regadrella phoenix*. Many *Cidaris cidaris* and *Bathynectes maravigna* were seen in these ecosystems. Comparatively, ridge areas with elevated slopes showed an exuberant increase of diversity, besides the *Errina atlantica* and *Anthomastus/Pseudoanthomastus* sp., it has large *Paragorgia johnsoni* of two morphotypes (white and red), *Placogorgia* sp., *Leiopathes expansa*, *Narella bellissima* and *Pleurocorallium johnsoni*. The sponge fauna has changed to the lamellar *Desmacella grimaldii*, *Poecillastra compressa* and the big tubular *Xestospongia friabilis*. Deeper areas (around 900 m) with volcanic rock outcrops and pillow lavas, presented the typical fauna of the MAR VMEs ecosystems, such as *Leiopathes expansa*, *Lophelia pertusa*, *Placogorgia* sp., *Hemicorallium tricolor*, *H. niobe*, *Chrysogorgia* sp. and *Acanella arbuscula*. At these depths the hexactinellids the *Hertwigia falcifera*, *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Regadrella phoenix*, *Farrea occa* were the most frequent sponge’s species observed. Going up the slope, at intermediate depths, also a large dense garden of *Candidella imbricata* with *Narella versluysi* was detected, with several other species emerging from rock outcrops (e.g., *L. expansa*, *A. arbuscula*, *H. tricolor* and *E. atlantica*, to name a few).

Figure 65. Bathymetric map showing the five dives conducted on the 6th September of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago in Ferradura area.

Figure 66. Screenshots taken from the video footage recorded on the 6th September of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago Ferradura area.

07 September 2024

We arrived at Horta harbour at about 05:00, after the last transit of the MapGES 2024 ARQ cruise. We left the RV Arquipélago at 07:00 with all the gear organized and the laboratories cleaned. This was the end of the MapGES 2024 cruise on-board the RV Arquipélago.

5.4 LIFE ON BOARD OF RV ARQUIPÉLAGO DURING LEG 1 OF THE MAPGES 2024 CRUISE

5.5 LIFE ON BOARD OF RV ARQUIPÉLAGO DURING LEG 2 OF THE MAPGES 2024 CRUISE

5.6 LIFE ON BOARD OF RV ARQUIPÉLAGO DURING LEG 4 OF THE MAPGES 2024 CRUISE

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Reference: Morato, T., G. Gonçalves, L. Rodrigues, J. Balsa, G. Cardoso, S. Gomes, R. Lacoste, M.N. Engesser, M. Ramos, G.H. Taranto, M.P. Vilavendrell, M. Carreiro-Silva, C. Dominguez-Carrió (2024). MapGES 2024 Cruise Report: Exploration and mapping of deep-sea biodiversity in the Azores on board the RV Arquipélago. Azores Deep-Sea Research Group, Institute of Marine Sciences - Okeanos, University of The Azores, Portugal. 78pp. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14774840

